

ANNEX A

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION OF THE SCIENTIFIC DATA ANALYSIS FOR THE SPACE ASTROMETRY MISSION

HIPPARCOS

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1. INTRODUCTION: DATA PROCESSING AND THE OBSERVATION MODEL

This Annex contains a detailed mathematical formulation of the more important stages of the scientific processing of HIPPARCOS data as currently planned by the Northern Data Analysis Consortium. Its contents can roughly be divided in two parts. Sections 2-8 give a fairly complete description of the observation model, while Sections 9-15 and part of Section 7 describe various stages of the data processing as based on this model.

The terms 'observation model' and 'data processing' are best explained in terms of two different categories of physical variables used in this context, viz. observables and parameters. The observables, which are variables immediately available to observation, are in this case:

- (a) the complete record of IDT pulse counts $\{N_k\}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, \sim 10^{11}$;
- (b) the record of Star Mapper counts $\{N_k^*\}$;
- (c) the complete record of gyro output samples $\{g_j\}$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, \sim 10^9$, where each sample is an n -vector for the $n \geq 3$ gyros;
- (d) housekeeping data such as temperatures inside the instrument etc.; these are however not discussed in the following.

The model parameters characterize the idealized physical system (stars plus instrument) at any given time. Choosing an appropriate set of model parameters is to some extent arbitrary and perhaps the most critical part of the construction of an observation model. The model parameters used here are basically:

- (A) the five astrometric parameters $\{\alpha_0, \delta_0, \mu_\alpha, \mu_\delta, \tilde{\omega}\}$ per programme star;
- (B) three time-dependent attitude angles $\alpha_2(t), \delta_2(t), \omega(t)$;
- (C) 10 to 20 time dependent large-scale distortion parameters $\{G_{fkl}(t)\}$;
- (D) modulation and phase parameters M_1, M_2, v_2 depending on time and position in the field.

The observation model can be regarded as a recipe for computing expected values for the observables and their covariances, when values have been assigned to the model parameters. Conversely, the data processing aims at obtaining good estimates of the model parameters, together with their uncertainties, from values of the observables obtained by observation. The data processing leans heavily on the observation model since the parameters are in principle found by adjusting their values until acceptable agreement is obtained between the observables as computed via the observation model and their actually observed values. In simpler data processing tasks such adjustment would typically be carried out using least-squares, maximum likelihood, or Bayesian techniques.

The data processing described here is based on the maximum likelihood approach, although the adjustment of parameters proceeds, for practical reasons, via a number of auxiliary variables such as Star Mapper transit times, grid coordinates, and star abscissae.

The observation model starts with a description of the apparent motion of stars on the sky (Section 2); then their motions with respect to the modulating slits are described via the telescope attitude (Section 3) and instrument parameters (Sections 4-5). Finally the IDT, Star Mapper, and gyro signals are derived by application of additional parameters characterizing these detectors (Sections 6-8).

The logical beginning of the data processing is the derivation of Star Mapper transits (Section 7), which are used with gyro data for the attitude reconstitution (Section 9). The motions of stellar images on the grid are obtained by the IDT data processing (Section 10) and combined in set solutions (Section 11) to yield instantaneous one-dimensional positions on the sky (abscissae). Celestial coordinates are recovered by the PRS solution and back-substitution (Sections 12-13). The particular problems caused by multiple stars are briefly treated in Section 14. Section 15 contains a proposal for defining a unique HIPPARCOS system by global adjustment to the FK5.

The reader is referred to Appendix A for an explanation of vector notations etc. used in the following. Some specific numerical or algorithmic problems are addressed in Appendices B, C, and D.

2. CELESTIAL COORDINATE SYSTEM; COMPUTATION OF APPARENT POSITIONS

The celestial coordinate system adopted for the scientific data processing will serve as an inertial reference frame for the orbital and attitude motions of the satellite, while being at the same time subject to refinement by the data processing. Since a celestial coordinate system can in reality only be defined by means of a catalogue of stellar positions and proper motions, the adopted system $\tilde{E}$ will be defined by (a subset of) the latest update of the working catalogue. The working catalogue coincides with the input and output catalogues before and after the data processing, respectively.

It is important to realize that the quality of $\tilde{E}$ from the point of view of Hipparcos is measured only by the degree of internal consistency, i.e. the degree to which true angles between stars equal the angles computed from the catalogue. In this respect the quality of $\tilde{E}$ is improved from something of the order of 1" (e.g. FK4 $\subset$ input catalogue) to a few milliarcsec (output catalogue). Contrary to the internal consistency, the external "absoluteness" of

the system, i.e. the errors of orientation and rotation with respect e.g. to the equator and equinoxes, is not in the least improved by the data reductions.

Since, from a computational point of view, there is no real advantage of using one particular (inertial) system rather than another, we adopt the system preferred for the output catalogue, namely an equatorial system referred to the mean equator and equinox of the date J2000.0. Thus $\underline{E} = (\underline{x}_E \ \underline{y}_E \ \underline{z}_E)$, where $\underline{x}_E$ and $\underline{z}_E$ are unit vectors in the directions of the mean vernal equinox and mean north equatorial pole, respectively, of J2000.0, and $\underline{y}_E = \underline{z}_E \wedge \underline{x}_E$.

Let $\underline{u}$ be the unit vector in the direction of a star (or minor planet) as viewed from the moving satellite. The apparent position of the object with respect to $\underline{E}$, i.e. $\underline{E}'\underline{u}$, must at any instant be computable from catalogue data (astrometric parameters or ephemeris) and auxiliary data such as the barycentric motion of the satellite (i.e. motion with respect to the mass center of the Solar System). The required accuracy in $\underline{E}'\underline{u}$, assuming error-free catalogue data, must be considerably better than the precision of the final catalogue, i.e. a fraction of a milliarcsec (mas). For a star, the computation of $\underline{E}'\underline{u}$ amounts to taking into account its proper motion and parallax, stellar aberration, and gravitational light deflection caused by the Sun and possibly other bodies of the Solar System.

Given the astrometric parameters α_0 , δ_0 , μ_α , μ_δ , $\tilde{\omega}$, and the radial velocity v_R (if known) of a star, its barycentric position ($\underline{r}$) and velocity ($\dot{\underline{r}}$) at time t_0 (mid-time of mission) are:

$$\underline{r}(t_0) = R \tilde{\omega}^{-1} \underline{u}_0 \quad (2.1)$$

$$\dot{\underline{r}}(t_0) = v_R \underline{u}_0 + R \tilde{\omega}^{-1} \dot{\underline{u}}_0 \quad (2.2)$$

where R is the astronomical unit and

$$\underline{E}'\underline{u}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \delta_0 \cos \alpha_0 \\ \cos \delta_0 \sin \alpha_0 \\ \sin \delta_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\underline{E}'\dot{\underline{u}}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos \delta_0 \sin \alpha_0 \mu_\alpha - \sin \delta_0 \cos \alpha_0 \mu_\delta \\ \cos \delta_0 \cos \alpha_0 \mu_\alpha - \sin \delta_0 \sin \alpha_0 \mu_\delta \\ \cos \delta_0 \mu_\delta \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.4)$$

(Following usual practice, light-time effects due to the star's motion are not included in the definition of its space motion.) Assuming rectilinear space motions of the star and the Solar System barycentre, the barycentric unit vector towards the star at time $t = t_0 + \tau$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\bar{u}} &= [\underline{r}(t_0) + \tau \dot{\underline{r}}] \cdot |\underline{r}(t_0) + \tau \dot{\underline{r}}|^{-1} \\ &= \underline{u}_0 + \tau \dot{\underline{u}}_0 - \tau^2 [R^{-1} \tilde{\omega} v_R \dot{\underline{u}}_0 + \frac{1}{2} |\dot{\underline{u}}_0|^2 \underline{u}_0] + O(\tau^3). \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Assuming $|\tau| < 3$ yr, $\tilde{\omega} < 1''$, $|v_R| < 300$ km s⁻¹, and $|\dot{\underline{u}}_0| < 20''$ yr⁻¹, the error of the second-order formula is $|O(\tau^3)| < 0.1$ mas.

The satellitocentric coordinate direction is

$$\underline{\bar{u}} = \underline{u} + (\underline{I} - \underline{u}\underline{u}') \rho_0 \tilde{\omega} \quad (2.6)$$

where ρ_0 is the coordinate direction from the satellite to the barycentre and $\tilde{\omega}$ is the parallax.

The direction $\underline{\bar{u}}$ differs from the observed direction because of relativistic light deflexion and aberration. Following Murray (1981) we define the 'natural frame' at an observer to be the locally inertial frame which is instantaneously at rest relative to the barycentric frame. The direction $\underline{\hat{u}}$ relative to the natural frame will be referred to as the 'natural' direction and can be expressed in the form

$$\underline{\hat{u}} = (\underline{I} + \underline{\Gamma}) \underline{\bar{u}} \quad \underline{\Gamma} = \frac{2GM/c^2}{|\rho_0| \{ |\rho_0| - \rho_0' \underline{\bar{u}} \}} (\rho_0 \wedge \underline{\bar{u}}) \wedge \quad (\text{when } w \ll 1) \quad (2.7)$$

where $\underline{\Gamma}$ is a relativistic tensor which depends on the form of the metric describing the gravitational field. Murray (1981) gives the natural direction for the general relativistic spherically symmetric static field, but for Hipparcos it may be necessary to consider a more complicated metric to take account of the planets; this will be investigated.

The 'proper' direction, $\underline{u}$, as seen by a moving observer is obtained from the natural direction by the Lorentz transformation

$$\underline{u} = \frac{\underline{L}(\underline{\hat{u}} + c^{-1} \underline{\hat{v}})}{1 + c^{-1} \underline{\hat{u}}' \underline{\hat{v}}} \quad (2.8)$$

where $\underline{\hat{v}}$ is the instantaneous velocity of the observer relative to the natural frame and

$$\underline{L} = (1 - c^{-2} \underline{\hat{v}}' \underline{\hat{v}})^{\frac{1}{2}} \underline{I} + [1 + (1 - c^{-2} \underline{\hat{v}}' \underline{\hat{v}})^{\frac{1}{2}}]^{-1} \underline{\hat{v}} \underline{\hat{v}}' \quad (2.9)$$

is the Lorentz tensor.

For 0.1 mas accuracy the barycentric velocity of the satellite, $\underline{\hat{v}}$, should be known to about 0.15 m s⁻¹. The gravitational deflexion by the Sun amounts to 2 - 10 mas; otherwise only the deflexions by Jupiter and Saturn must be considered.

3. THE TELESCOPE SYSTEM AND ATTITUDE

The telescope system $\underline{T}$ is fixed with respect to the optical instrument. The orientation of $\underline{T}$ with respect to the celestial system $\underline{E}$, the telescope attitude, is given by the transformation $\underline{T}'\underline{E}$. $\underline{T} = (\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z})$ is such that $\underline{x}$ is along the internal bisector of the basic angle, $\underline{z}$ is along the nominal spin axis, always with the solar panels on the +z side of the satellite, and $\underline{y} = \underline{z} \wedge \underline{x}$. The precise definition is closely related to the modelisation of instrument and observations and is further discussed in Section 6. For present purposes the following definition is adequate. Let $\underline{p}_1, \underline{p}_2$ be unit vectors in the directions of two imaginary stars that would be imaged on the same point at the adopted centre of the modulating grid. Indices are chosen so that $\underline{p}_2 \wedge \underline{p}_1$ points to the solar panel side of the telescope. Then

$$\underline{p}_2' \underline{p}_1 = \cos \gamma, \quad (3.1)$$

$$\underline{x} = (\underline{p}_2 + \underline{p}_1) / |\underline{p}_2 + \underline{p}_1|, \quad \underline{z} = (\underline{p}_2 \wedge \underline{p}_1) / |\underline{p}_2 \wedge \underline{p}_1|, \quad \underline{y} = \underline{z} \wedge \underline{x}, \quad (3.2)$$

where γ is the basic angle. The plane containing $\underline{p}_1$ and $\underline{p}_2$ is known as the principal plane; it contains also $\underline{x}$ and $\underline{y}$ and is normal to $\underline{z}$.

The telescope attitude is given by the (3,3)-matrix $\underline{T}'\underline{E}$. However, only three independent quantities are needed to specify the attitude, e.g. three Euler angles. The selected attitude angles $\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega$ are such that a triad of unit vectors initially aligned with $\underline{E}$ becomes $\underline{T}$ after three successive rotations:

- (i) by an angle $\alpha_z + \frac{1}{2}\pi$ about the original z axis;
- (ii) by an angle $\frac{1}{2}\pi - \delta_z$ about the resulting x axis; and
- (iii) by an angle ω about the resulting z axis.

Thus

$$\underline{T}'\underline{E} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \omega & \sin \omega & 0 \\ -\sin \omega & \cos \omega & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sin \delta_z & \cos \delta_z \\ 0 & -\cos \delta_z & \sin \delta_z \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \alpha_z & \cos \alpha_z & 0 \\ -\cos \alpha_z & -\sin \alpha_z & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \omega \sin \delta_z \cos \alpha_z - \cos \omega \sin \alpha_z \\ -\cos \omega \sin \delta_z \cos \alpha_z + \sin \omega \sin \alpha_z \\ \cos \delta_z \cos \alpha_z \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \omega \sin \delta_z \sin \alpha_z + \cos \omega \cos \alpha_z & \sin \omega \cos \delta_z \\ -\cos \omega \sin \delta_z \sin \alpha_z - \sin \omega \cos \alpha_z & \cos \omega \cos \delta_z \\ \cos \delta_z \sin \alpha_z & \sin \delta_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.3)$$

The attitude angles have a simple astronomical meaning: $(\alpha_z \ \delta_z)$ is the celestial coordinates of $\underline{z}$, while ω defines the rotational phase about the z axis, measured as the angle in the principal plane from the equator to $\underline{x}$. Due to the revolving scanning law $|\delta_z| \lesssim \xi + 23.5^\circ \lesssim 68.5^\circ$, where ξ is the Sun/spin axis angle. This prevents the attitude representation $(\alpha_z \ \delta_z \ \omega)$ from ever becoming singular during normal operation of the satellite.

Due to the continuously varying attitude angles, $\underline{T}$ is rotating with respect to an inertial system with instantaneous angular velocity $\underline{\omega}$. Because a gyroscope senses the component of $\underline{\omega}$ along its input axis, which is fixed with respect to the telescope, we need the components of $\underline{\omega}$ along the telescope axes, i.e. $\underline{T}'\underline{\omega} = (\omega_x \ \omega_y \ \omega_z)'$ expressed in terms of $\dot{\alpha}_z, \dot{\delta}_z, \dot{\omega}$. To this end we observe that $\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z$ are components of the (3,3)-matrix $(\underline{T}'\underline{\omega})_\wedge = \underline{T}'\underline{\omega} \wedge \underline{T}$ [eqn (A.7)] = $\underline{T}'\underline{E}(d/dt)(\underline{E}'\underline{T})$, where $\underline{E}'\underline{T}$ is the transpose of (3.3). A direct computation yields

$$\underline{T}'\underline{\omega} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \delta_z \sin \omega & -\cos \omega & 0 \\ \cos \delta_z \cos \omega & \sin \omega & 0 \\ \sin \delta_z & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{\alpha}_z \\ \dot{\delta}_z \\ \dot{\omega} \end{pmatrix} = \underline{D} \underline{\dot{a}}, \quad (3.4)$$

where $\underline{D}$ denotes the (3,3)-matrix being a function of δ_z and ω , and $\underline{a} = (\alpha_z \ \delta_z \ \omega)'$. Eqn (3.4) is the kinematic equation of the attitude motion. Attitude reconstitution based on an initial attitude $\underline{a}_0$ and subsequent gyro readings basically amounts to integrating the first-order differential equation $\underline{\dot{a}} = \underline{D}^{-1}(\underline{T}'\underline{\omega})$, where

$$\underline{D}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \sec \delta_z \sin \omega & \sec \delta_z \cos \omega & 0 \\ -\cos \omega & \sin \omega & 0 \\ -\tan \delta_z \sin \omega & -\tan \delta_z \cos \omega & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

and $\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}$ follows from the gyro readings.

4. FIELD COORDINATES AND GRID GEOMETRY

Given the apparent celestial position of an object, $E'u$, and the telescope attitude $T'E$, the object direction with respect to the telescope is $T'u = (T'E)(E'u)$. When observed, the direction u must be close to either p_1 or p_2 ; it is then convenient to refer it to the nearest line of sight p_f by means of small angular displacements η , ζ parallel and perpendicular to the principal plane:

$$u = \cos \zeta \cos \eta p_f + \cos \zeta \sin \eta z_{\wedge} p_f + \sin \zeta z. \quad (4.1)$$

η , ζ are called the field coordinates of the object. The field index f is given by the sign of the y component of u :

$$f = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } y'u \geq 0, \\ 2 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

If the telescope spins about z in the positive sense, the image of an inertially fixed object will pass through the two fields at a constant height ζ above the principal plane and with uniformly decreasing η . Because the slits of the main (IDT) grid are approximately aligned with the curves of constant η , the phase of the intensity modulation behind the grid would ideally give that coordinate directly. In reality a more complicated model of the mapping from grid to field coordinates must be employed. The choice of model may depend on the way the grid is manufactured and on the character of optical distortions; the present formulation is rather intended as an example and a useful starting point.

At the adopted centre of the grid $(\eta \ \zeta) = (0 \ 0)$. Any point g on the grid is projected by the optical system onto two points on the celestial sphere, the field coordinates of which are $\eta_f(g)$, $\zeta_f(g)$, $f = 1, 2$. Note that although $\eta_1(g) \approx \eta_2(g)$ and $\zeta_1(g) \approx \zeta_2(g)$, strict equality cannot be assumed (except for the grid centre), since the projections go through different parts of the optics for which distortion may be different. Let the slits of the main grid be numbered $G = 1, 2, \dots, n_G \approx 2700$. The projections on the sky of the curve along the centre of a particular slit may be described by two functions $\eta = \eta_f(G, \zeta)$, $f = 1, 2$, for integer G defined by $\eta_f(G, \zeta) = \eta_f(g)$, where g is the point on the centre of slit G for which $\zeta_f(g) = \zeta$. By interpolation to non-integer values of G the functions $\eta_f(G, \zeta)$ become continuous and we may define inverse functions $G = G_f(\eta, \zeta)$, $f = 1, 2$, mapping the field coordinates onto the continuous grid coordinate G . The mathematical form of these functions could be the following:

$$G_f(\eta, \zeta) = \delta G(\eta, \zeta) + G_{f00} + G_{f10}\eta + G_{f01}\zeta + G_{f20}\eta^2 + G_{f11}\eta\zeta + G_{f02}\zeta^2 + \dots \quad (4.3)$$

where $\delta G(\eta, \zeta)$ is the laboratory calibration of the effective distortion, averaged between the fields, and $G_{fk\ell}$ are instrument constants describing residual distortion to be determined in the course of the data processing.

The star mapper grid consists of one group of vertical slits (i.e. parallel to those of the main grid) and another group of inclined slits, which may be chevroned or discontinuous. Because of the relaxed requirements compared to the main grid, only the central line of each group needs detailed specification. This may be in the form of four functions $\eta = \eta_{fg}(\zeta)$, $f = 1, 2$, where $g = 1, 2$ respectively for the vertical and inclined group. The functions may be (piecewise) polynomial, e.g.

$$\eta_{fg}(\zeta) = e_{g0} + e_{g1}\zeta + e_{g2}\zeta^2 - (-1)^f d_g. \quad (4.4)$$

The coefficients e_{gk} , d_g are imperfectly known from laboratory measurements and should be refined in the data processing.

5. GEOMETRY OF OBSERVATIONS

In this Section we derive difference formulae showing how small errors in the assumed object direction and telescope attitude produce observable errors in the field coordinates η , ζ . Although further transformations are needed before they can be applied in the data processing, the present form of the observation equations are particularly helpful to explain how the observations work, and especially why the attitude need not be very accurately known.

From (3.1), (3.2), and (4.1) we have

$$\underline{T}'\underline{u} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \zeta \cos(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) \\ \cos \zeta \sin(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) \\ \sin \zeta \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

where the upper and lower signs refer to the fields $f = 1$ and 2 respectively. The observed field coordinates, derived from the IDT and star mapper signals, generally differ from the ones computed from (5.1) by small amounts $\Delta\eta$, $\Delta\zeta$, defined in the sense 'observed minus computed', O-C. The difference may be attributed to required corrections $\Delta(\underline{T}'\underline{E})$ and $\Delta(\underline{E}'\underline{u})$ to the assumed attitude and object direction. The correction to the attitude can be represented by a small misorientation vector $\underline{\epsilon}$, $\Delta(\underline{T}'\underline{E}) = (\underline{\Delta T})'\underline{E} = (\underline{\epsilon} \wedge \underline{T})'\underline{E}$, while $\Delta(\underline{E}'\underline{u}) = \underline{E}'\underline{\Delta u}$. Differentiating (5.1) we obtain

$$(\underline{\varepsilon}_{\wedge} \underline{T})' \underline{u} + \underline{T}' \underline{\Delta u} = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos \zeta \sin(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) & -\sin \zeta \cos(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) \\ \cos \zeta \cos(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) & -\sin \zeta \sin(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) \\ 0 & \cos \zeta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\Delta\gamma \\ \Delta\zeta \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.2)$$

Putting $\underline{\Delta z} = \underline{\varepsilon}_{\wedge} \underline{z}$, we obtain for the vertical field coordinate the differential

$$\Delta\zeta = \sec \zeta (z' \underline{\Delta u} + u' \underline{\Delta z}) \quad (5.3)$$

Thus the component of the object direction error along $\underline{z}$ and the misorientation of $\underline{z}$ along the object direction go fully into $\Delta\zeta$, since $\sec \zeta \approx 1$.

For the other field coordinate elimination of $\Delta\zeta$ yields

$$(\Delta\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\Delta\gamma) \cos^2 \zeta = (-y' \underline{u} \quad x' \underline{u} \quad 0) \underline{T}' (\underline{\Delta u} - \underline{\varepsilon}_{\wedge} \underline{u}). \quad (5.4)$$

Introducing the unit vector normal to $\underline{z}$ and $\underline{u}$, viz. $\underline{s} = \sec \zeta \underline{\varepsilon}_{\wedge} \underline{u}$, we have

$$(-y' \underline{u} \quad x' \underline{u} \quad 0) \underline{T}' = \cos \zeta \underline{s}' \quad (5.5)$$

and hence

$$\Delta\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\Delta\gamma = \sec \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\Delta u} - \sec \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\varepsilon}_{\wedge} \underline{u}. \quad (5.6)$$

Writing $\underline{u} = \cos \zeta \underline{\varepsilon}_{\wedge} \underline{z} + \sin \zeta \underline{z}$ it is seen that

$$\underline{s}' \underline{\varepsilon}_{\wedge} \underline{u} = \cos \zeta \underline{z}' \underline{\varepsilon} + \sin \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\Delta z}, \quad (5.7)$$

so we finally obtain

$$\Delta\eta = \sec \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\Delta u} - \underline{z}' \underline{\varepsilon} - \tan \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\Delta z} \mp \frac{1}{2}\Delta\gamma. \quad (5.8)$$

Equation (5.8) is fundamental for the principle of observation by Hipparcos. The first term $\sec \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\Delta u}$ is the object's positional error in the scanning direction (since $\underline{s}$ is in the principal plane) multiplied by a factor ≈ 1 . The second term $-\underline{z}' \underline{\varepsilon}$ is the attitude error about the spin axis ($\underline{z}$). This is independent of $\underline{u}$ and consequently the same for all stars visible in the instrument; it is virtually eliminated by making quasi-simultaneous relative measurements of two or more stars. The third term $-\tan \zeta \underline{s}' \underline{\Delta z}$ is the component along $\underline{s}$ of the displacement of $\underline{z}$, multiplied by a numerically small factor, $|\tan \zeta| < 0.01$; hence $\underline{\Delta z}$ need not be known better than about 0.1" for sub-mas accuracy in $\Delta\eta$. $\underline{\Delta z}$ is in effect determined from star mapper observations, yielding observation equations of the form (5.3), and using gyro readings for attitude interpolation. The fourth term finally is the error in the assumed value for the basic angle, which can be determined from a closed chain of observations along a great circle scan.

6. MODEL OF IDT SIGNAL

The raw IDT signal is the sequence of pulse counts N_k , consisting at least for the fainter stars of the number of photoelectrons per sample interval $t_{k-1} = t_k - \Delta t \leq t < t_k$, where the constant sampling period Δt is of the order of 1 ms. The photoelectron counts N_k are assumed to follow the Poisson distribution,

$$\Pr[N_k = n | I(t), t_{k-1} \leq t < t_k] = (n!)^{-1} \lambda^n \exp(-\lambda), \quad (6.1)$$

where the expected number of counts, $E(N_k) = \lambda = \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} I(t) dt$. Note that the "intensity" $I(t)$ refers not to the light intensity (energy flux), but to the expected frequency of counts as function of time; so detector quantum efficiency, dark count rate, etc., are implicit. For bright stars N_k may be the amplified detector current, integrated for the same time interval, and truncated to an integer value. Since it is often found that analogue detector signals, after suitable scaling, approximately follow a continuous version of the Poisson distribution, such samples can probably be processed in much the same way as the photoelectron counts. Indeed, if the signal processing is regarded as a minimum-variance estimation of certain parameters, the only relevant property of the distribution (6.1) is that the variance of N_k equals the expectation of N_k , $\text{Var}(N_k) = E[(N_k - \lambda)^2] = \lambda$. Since a scaling factor c can always be found (possibly weakly depending on λ) such that $\text{Var}(cN_k) = E(cN_k)$, the optimum processing of photoelectron counts and scaled analogue values become identical. (Such scaling actually amounts to substituting the "detective quantum efficiency", DQE, for the quantum efficiency.) We shall subsequently regard N_k as being equivalent to photoelectron counts, in this respect, although the numbers are no longer necessarily integers. Moreover, it will be assumed that the (scaled) counts of different time intervals are statistically independent,

$$\text{Cov}(N_k, N_\ell) = E\{[N_k - E(N_k)][N_\ell - E(N_\ell)]\} = \delta_{k\ell} E(N_k) \quad (6.2)$$

($\delta_{k\ell}$ = Kronecker's delta).

If the attitude motion $\underline{a}(t)$ is known, the formulae of the preceding sections allow the grid coordinate for an object of given position $\underline{E}'_u$ to be computed as function of time, $G(t)$. Because the grid transmittance is locally (i.e. on a scale comparable to the size of the diffraction image) very nearly periodical in G , the period being = 1 by definition, we may write the intensity in the form

$$I(t) = B + I_0 \left[1 + \sum_{\ell=1}^m M_\ell \cos[2\pi\ell G(t) - v_\ell] \right] \quad (6.3)$$

where I_0 , M_ℓ , and v_ℓ are slowly varying functions of f , η , and ζ ; B is the background contribution and $m = \text{entier}[D/(G_{f10} \lambda_{\min})] \approx 3$ is the number of signal harmonics supported by the telescope optical transfer function ($D =$ aperture length normal to z , $\lambda_{\min} =$ shortest wavelength detected, $1/G_{f10} =$ grid period). M_ℓ and v_ℓ depend in general also on the colour of the object, and I_0 of course on its magnitude.

Recalling that integer values of G were assigned to points on the slit centres, we may now qualify the notion of "slit centre" by putting $v_1 = 0$ for both fields and at all points of the grid. Thus the image is by definition at the centre of a slit when the first harmonic of $I(t)$ is at a maximum. For $\ell = 2, 3$, the functions $v_\ell(f, \eta, \zeta, C)$, where $C =$ colour index, express the phase errors of the higher harmonics with respect to the first. Due to asymmetry of aberrations and slit transmittance, they are in general non-zero.

As a first approximation $M_\ell(f, \eta, \zeta, C)$, $\ell = 1, 2, 3$, and $v_\ell(f, \eta, \zeta, C)$, $\ell = 2, 3$, are obtained from laboratory measurements and theoretical calculations, but are then refined by observation of relatively bright single stars. They may require frequent updating, as they probably depend rather critically on the focussing.

Integrating (6.3) over the interval $t_{k-1} \leq t < t_k$ we obtain

$$E(N_k) = B\Delta t + I_0 \Delta t \left[1 + \sum_{\ell=1}^m M_\ell \cos[2\pi\ell G_k - v_\ell] \right], \quad (6.4)$$

where $G_k = G(t_k - \frac{1}{2}\Delta t)$ and we have redefined the modulation coefficients, $M_\ell := M_\ell \text{sinc}(\pi\ell G\Delta t)$, which is possible thanks to the relative constancy of $\dot{G}$.

A preliminary optimisation of the main grid parameters (Lindgren, 1979-12-13) yields a grid period $1/G_{f10} \approx 1.1$ arcsec and (slit width)/(period)-ratio ≈ 0.36 , for which $M_1 \approx 0.73$, $M_2 \approx 0.32$, and $M_3 \approx 0.01$. The smallness of M_3 depends partly on its frequency being near the optical transfer function cut-off, but also on the slit width being close to one third of the grid period. For the IDT signal processing it is safely neglected, with a substantial reduction of the amount of computations and number of parameters to be fitted.

7. MODELISATION AND PROCESSING OF STAR MAPPER SIGNAL

The star mapper signal is primarily intended for determination of the telescope attitude, whether in real time, as required for the construction of observation sequences and piloting of the IDT, or a posteriori (Section 9). In addition to this, a continuously recorded star mapper signal would yield an enormous amount of valuable photometric and astrometric information, if exploited as a means to observe systematically all stars to a certain magnitude limit (project TYCHO).

In this section we are mainly concerned with signal processing for the purpose of posterior attitude reconstitution. This permits considerable simplification because

- (a) the attitude is known, from the real-time determination, to a few arcsec;
- (b) only transits of stars with positions computable to about 1" or better need to be processed; these are normally brighter than $B = 10$.

The occurrence of a transit is therefore predictable to better than 0.05 sec of time. This uncertainty is small enough, compared to the average interval between transits (a few seconds for $B < 10$), to reduce the frequency of misidentification or signal confusion to a level which can reasonably be coped with, in the attitude reconstitution, by simple rejection criteria based on the analysis of residuals.

We attempt, nevertheless, a somewhat broader treatment, in that the star mapper signal processing is regarded as a sequential detection/estimation problem, presupposing (for a lack of details on alternative modes) that the complete sequence of pulse counts, sampled at a fixed rate, is available for the scientific data analysis. Narrowing down to the more restricted needs of attitude determination is a trivial modification.

As for the IDT signal, the star mapper counts N_k^* (scaled if necessary) are assumed to follow the Poisson distribution with expectation

$$E(N_k^*) = \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} I^*(t) dt. \quad (7.1)$$

The sample interval $\Delta t^* = t_k - t_{k-1}$ may be an integer multiple of the IDT sample interval Δt . (Quantities related to the star mapper is distinguished, when necessary, from corresponding quantities of the IDT by means of the asterisk.) The signal intensity $I^*(t)$ is supposed to arise by linear (incoherent) superposition of a background intensity $B^*(t)$ and the individual responses to the different stars present in the star mapper field of view. Thus, if $\eta_i(t)$, $\tau_i(t)$, f_i are the field coordinates and field index of a star designated i , and

I_i , C_i respectively its brightness and colour, we have quite generally

$$I^*(t) = B^*(t) + \sum_i I_i S[\eta_i(t), \zeta_i(t), f_i, C_i], \quad (7.2)$$

where $S(\eta, \zeta, f, C)$ is the star mapper response to a point-source image of unit brightness.

Equation (7.2) is not a practically useful model, though, partly because adequate numerical representation of the general response function S would be far too bulky, but mainly because it does not lend itself to simple and efficient processing of large quantities of data. To obtain a tractable model we shall provisionally introduce a number of approximations to be stated below. Some of them are likely to be revised or withdrawn at some later stage, but for the present it is expedient not to burden the presentation with too many details.

It is recalled that the star mapper grid will consist of two differently inclined slit groups, indicated by group index $g = 1, 2$. The central line of each group is described by equations $\eta_{fg}(\zeta)$, depending also, although very little, on the field index f (Section 4). The transit of star # i at one of the groups occurs at a time τ satisfying the equation

$$\eta_i(\tau) - \eta_{f,g}[\zeta_i(\tau)] = 0. \quad (7.3)$$

It is noted, furthermore, that the passage of a star across a group takes a few tenths of a second only; consequently, there is seldom more than one star contributing significantly to the sum in (7.2), at any given moment. Most of the time no star contributes.

The following approximations are provisionally adopted:

- (i) Each passage of a star across one group is considered a separate entity normally undisturbed by other passages; disturbed passages are thus regarded as abnormal and would be subject to special treatment (rejection or correction) at a later stage of the processing.
- (ii) $B^*(t)$ is regarded as a slowly varying function of time, which could be accurately determined from the intervals between passages and interpolated to the passages; in particular, it is regarded as constant during a single passage.
- (iii) Colour (C) dependence of S is neglected. This may be a doubtful approximation, but it should not introduce systematic errors, as it is mainly the MTF, and not so much the PTF, which depends on the wavelength. (In other words, stars of different colours may give response peaks of varying sharpness, but they are not significantly

displaced from each other.)

- (iv) The response function S depends only on the coordinate difference $\eta - \eta_{fg}(\zeta)$, and not on η and ζ independently; this presupposes that the slits are parallel within a group (in the sense that their separations in η are independent of ζ), and that the OTF is reasonably constant over the star mapper field.
- (v) The passage of a star across a single group is short enough that its vertical motion ($\dot{\zeta}$) and horizontal acceleration ($\ddot{\eta}$), along with higher derivatives, can be neglected.
- (vi) The response function S does not depend on the field (f) in other ways than through the functions $\eta_{fg}(\zeta)$. This is reasonable at least if the pupil shape is similar for the two fields.

According to (iii), (iv) and (vi) the response function can be decomposed as follows into group components $S^{(g)}$:

$$S(\eta, \zeta, f, C) := S^{(1)}[\eta - \eta_{f1}(\zeta)] + S^{(2)}[\eta - \eta_{f2}(\zeta)]. \quad (7.4)$$

By means of (v) and the definition of transit time (7.3), the arguments become

$$\eta(t) - \eta_{fg}[\zeta(t)] := (t - \tau)\dot{\eta}. \quad (7.5)$$

Defining a set of single-group response functions parametrized by g and $\dot{\eta}$,

$$S_{g\dot{\eta}}(\theta) \equiv \frac{1}{\Delta t^*} \int_{\theta - \Delta t^*}^{\theta} S^{(g)}(\theta\dot{\eta}) d\theta, \quad (7.6)$$

we finally arrive at the following signal model, locally applicable to all undisturbed passages:

$$E(N_k^*) = b + a S_{g\dot{\eta}}(t_k - \tau). \quad (7.7)$$

For brevity we introduce $b \equiv B^* \Delta t^*$, $a \equiv I_1 \Delta t^*$. The dependence on $\dot{\eta}$ is notationally suppressed in the sequel. In reality it must be allowed for if the deviations of $\dot{\eta}$ from its mean or nominal value, multiplied by the duration of a passage, exceeds a fraction of the Airy disk diameter.

The processing of a single passage now becomes a question of estimating b , a , τ , and, in the general case, g . One way of approach is by minimizing the least-squares functional

$$J(b, a, \tau, g) \equiv \sum_k W_g(t_k - \tau) [N_k^* - b - a S_g(t_k - \tau)]^2, \quad (7.8)$$

in which W_g is a non-negative a priori weight function; it should in particular be zero outside a finite interval restricting the range of summation.

Minimization of J with respect to the discrete variable g requires that the different cases ($g = 1, 2$) are separately tested and compared. Minimization with respect to τ is complicated by the existence of multiple minima (slit ambiguity), requiring a whole sequence of τ values to be tested in order that the global minimum be located. Minimization with respect to b and a , given trial values for τ and g , is on the other hand a straightforward process yielding the subfunctional

$$J(\tau, g) = \sum_k W_g(t_k - \tau) N_k^*{}^2 - [m_{g0} \hat{b}^2 + 2m_{g1} \hat{b} \hat{a} + m_{g2} \hat{a}^2], \quad (7.9)$$

where

$$\hat{b}(\tau, g) = \sum_k W_g(t_k - \tau) \frac{m_{g2} - m_{g1} S_g(t_k - \tau)}{m_{g0} m_{g2} - m_{g1}^2} N_k^*, \quad (7.10)$$

$$\hat{a}(\tau, g) = \sum_k W_g(t_k - \tau) \frac{-m_{g1} + m_{g0} S_g(t_k - \tau)}{m_{g0} m_{g2} - m_{g1}^2} N_k^*, \quad (7.11)$$

and the moments

$$m_{gj} = \sum_k W_g(t_k - \tau) [S_g(t_k - \tau)]^j, \quad j = 0, 1, 2 \quad (7.12)$$

are in practice independent of τ , given a short enough sampling interval and the continuity of S_g and W_g .

Calculating $\hat{b}$ and $\hat{a}$ for $g = 1, 2$ and a succession of trial values $\tau = \dots, t_{\ell-1}, t_{\ell}, t_{\ell+1}, \dots$ clearly amounts to applying four linear finite-length filters on the sequence of pulse counts. The filter coefficients are fixed except for the possible dependence on $\hat{n}$ mentioned in connexion with (7.7). To locate the global minimum of J in a rigorous way we must in addition compute the succession of weighted sums of $N_k^*{}^2$ and the bracketed expression in (7.9).

In practical cases it is found however that minimizing (7.8) is very nearly equivalent to maximizing $\hat{a}(\tau, g)$. This can perhaps be understood from (7.9) if it is observed that the weighted sum of $N_k^*{}^2$, for typical weight functions (such as $W_g = 1$ in an interval comprising the non-zero part of S_g), will exhibit a very shallow minimum, at most, near the true location, while the expression in brackets will increase monotonously with $\hat{a}$, thanks to the positiveness of m_{gj} and $\hat{b}$, and the relative constancy of $\hat{b}$. Thus it will suffice to pass the pulse counts through two linear filters, yielding the output sequences $\hat{a}_{g\ell} = \hat{a}(t_{\ell}, g)$, $g = 1, 2$. Estimated transit times $\hat{\tau}(g)$ are derived

by parabolic interpolation to the global maxima, whereupon the g corresponding to the higher maximum is selected.

When a longer stretch of data is filtered, in which several transits are expected, the "global maximum" should be interpreted as the supremum in a centred interval of length $2T$, where T is the duration of a passage from the first to the last slit in a group:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}(\hat{\tau}, g) \text{ is a global maximum} \\ \Leftrightarrow \\ \hat{a}(\hat{\tau}, g) \geq \hat{a}(\tau, g) \text{ for all } \tau \in [\hat{\tau} - T, \hat{\tau} + T]. \end{aligned} \quad (7.13)$$

In the context of sequential processing the search for global maxima in the above sense can be implemented with the aid of a finite-memory variable (p), e.g. according to the following algorithm (in which $M \propto T/\Delta t^*$ is the memory length):

```

{initial values:  n := 0,  p := 0,  k := previous point in sequence}
1  n := n + 1
   k := k + 1
   {compute new filter output  $\hat{a}_{gk}$ }
   if  $\hat{a}_{gk} > p$  then:
       n := 0
       p :=  $\hat{a}_{gk}$ 
       go to 1
   if n = M then:
       {global maximum = p has been found at point k-M}
       n := 0
       p := 0
   go to 1

```

Having thus located a global maximum of $\hat{a}_{gk}$, it should be tested first for statistical significance and then for possible deviations from the signal model (7.7). Such deviations may be due to faulty input data or overlapping transits.

The significance of $\hat{a}$ can be expressed in terms of the signal-to-noise ratio $SNR = \hat{a}/\sigma_{\hat{a}}$. If (7.11) is written more compactly as

$$\hat{a}_{gk} = \sum_n q_{gn} N_{k-n}^* \quad (7.14)$$

where q_{gn} are the filter coefficients, we find

$$\sigma_{\hat{a}}^2 = \mu_{g0} \hat{b} + \mu_{g1} \hat{a}, \quad (7.15)$$

where μ_{gj} are known constants,

$$\mu_{gj} = \sum_n q_{gn}^2 [S_g(n\Delta t^*)]^j, \quad j = 0, 1. \quad (7.16)$$

An estimate of the background level $\hat{b}$ is thus required for calculating SNR, but unlike $\hat{a}$, it need not be obtained at every point and not very accurately either. The maximum is accepted as significant if SNR exceeds a pre-set level.

Deviations from the signal model may be examined by means of normalized squared residuals,

$$r_k = [N_k^* - \hat{b} - \hat{a} S_g(t_k - \hat{\tau})]^2 [\hat{b} + \hat{a} S_g(t_k - \hat{\tau})]^{-1}, \quad (7.17)$$

which in the undisturbed case should follow the chi-square distribution with one degree of freedom. The kind of tests to be applied on the sequence of residuals will depend on which kinds of deviation are likely to occur, e.g. isolated gross deviations versus overlapping passages (the latter giving rather small deviations over a longer interval). The corrective actions will similarly depend on the distribution of deviations: if only very few isolated points deviate, these may be eliminated or replaced by interpolated values and the signal parameters recomputed; if overlapping passages are indicated, one may either reject the transit as a whole or try to disentangle the overlapping parts by feeding the residuals through the linear filters, etc. It is likely that any corrective action must be iterated.

8. MODEL OF GYRO SIGNALS

We assume that the satellite is equipped with four rate-integrating gyros, fairly rigidly connected to the telescope structure. Thus, the input axis of gyroscope no. i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$), $\underline{a}_i$, is approximately fixed with respect to the telescope system $\underline{T}$. Furthermore, we assume that the four gyros are synchronously sampled at a fixed frequency, probably in the range 5 - 50 Hz, and that the four gyro signals are fully available for the scientific data processing, together with relevant calibration data.

The output of gyro no. i for the sample interval $t_{j-1} = t_j - \delta t \leq t < t_j$ is

$$g_{ij} = k_i \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \underline{a}_i' \underline{\omega} dt + b_i \delta t + v_{ij} \quad (8.1)$$

where k_i is the scale factor (output pulses per radian), b_i is the drift rate, and v_{ij} white noise. Neglecting the variation of $\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}$ during the sampling period δt , we obtain the gyro signals vector

$$\underline{g}_j = \underline{K}(\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}) + \underline{b} + \underline{v}_j \quad (8.2)$$

where $\underline{b} = \delta t(b_1 \ b_2 \ b_3 \ b_4)'$, $\underline{v}_j = (v_{1j} \ v_{2j} \ v_{3j} \ v_{4j})'$, and $\underline{K}$ is the (almost) constant $(4,3)$ -matrix

$$\underline{K} = \delta t \begin{pmatrix} k_1 (\underline{T}'\underline{a}_1)' \\ k_2 (\underline{T}'\underline{a}_2)' \\ k_3 (\underline{T}'\underline{a}_3)' \\ k_4 (\underline{T}'\underline{a}_4)' \end{pmatrix} \quad (8.3)$$

From pre-flight calibrations we have preliminary estimates of $\underline{K}$ and $\underline{b}$, say $\tilde{\underline{K}}$, $\tilde{\underline{b}}$ (where the tilde $\sim$ denotes a priori quantities). The gyro signals model is then completed by statistical descriptions of $\underline{\Delta K} = \underline{K} - \tilde{\underline{K}}$, $\underline{\Delta b} = \underline{b} - \tilde{\underline{b}}$, and the noise covariance. For the time being it will be assumed that $\underline{\Delta K}$ is relatively constant over a considerable stretch of time (say, several days), while $\underline{\Delta b}$ is modelised as a Markov process with known time constant and covariance:

$$\underline{\Delta b}_{j+1} = \underline{M}_b \underline{\Delta b}_j + \underline{n}_{bj} \quad (8.4)$$

$$\underline{M}_b = \text{diag}\{\exp(-\delta t/\tau_{bi}), i = 1, 2, 3, 4\} \quad (8.5)$$

$$E(\underline{n}_{bj}) = \underline{0}, \quad \text{Cov}(\underline{n}_{bj}) = E(\underline{n}_{bj}\underline{n}_{bj}') = \text{diag}\{(2\sigma_{bi}^2 \delta t/\tau_{bi}), i = 1, 2, 3, 4\} \quad (8.6)$$

Typical values may be $\sigma_b \sim 0.01 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$ and $\tau_b \sim 10^5 \text{ s}$. The covariance of the white-noise component is

$$E(\underline{v}_j \underline{v}_j') = \sigma_v^2 \underline{I}, \quad (8.7)$$

where we may have $\sigma_v \sim 0.1 \text{ arcsec}$.

9. ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION

An accurate a posteriori attitude is required both for the (pre-)processing of IDT data (Section 10) and the set solutions (Section 11). The requirements are however qualitatively different for the two purposes, as explained below.

The IDT data pre-processing comprises a statistical estimation of the Fourier components of the modulated intensity, in which their phases (which later give the position of the image) are related to a reference modulation phase (H_k ; see Section 10). To ensure consistent results for the different stars observed in a 2 second interval (say), the error of the reference modulation phase must not fluctuate by more than about 0.1 modulation period over the time interval. In terms of the a posteriori angular velocity ($\hat{\omega}$) the requirement is

$$\left| \int_{T_0}^T \underline{z}' (\hat{\omega} - \underline{\omega}_{\text{true}}) dt \right| \lesssim 0.1 \text{ arcsec for } T_0 < T < T_0 + 2 \text{ s}. \quad (9.1)$$

This is basically a restriction on the rate error about the z axis. The requirements on the absolute attitude knowledge, $(\alpha_z \delta_z \omega)$, are on the other hand very relaxed (several arcsec).

The abscissae obtained from the set solutions are the projections of the stars onto a chosen reference great circle. In a 12 hour set the average ordinate (angular distance from the reference great circle) amounts to 1° . Since the actually measured coordinate (G or η) is in general inclined with respect to the reference great circle by a small angle $i \approx 1^\circ$, the projection typically involves a correction of about $1^\circ \tan i \approx 60 \text{ arcsec}$. The exact inclination is given by the coordinates of the star, z axis, and the pole of the reference great circle. It follows that the average projection error is less than 2 mas (which is certainly acceptable) if

$$\left| E'(\hat{z} - z_{\text{true}}) \right| < 0.1 \text{ arcsec}, \quad (9.2)$$

where $\hat{z}$ and z_{true} may be averaged over a 2 second interval. This requirement concerns the absolute attitude angles α_z and δ_z ; in contrast, there are no serious requirements on the knowledge of ω or the angular rates.

The attitude motion $\underline{a}(t)$ is in principle obtained by integration of the gyro signals, as indicated in Section 3, using star mapper observations for calibration of drift rates, scale factors, etc. A preliminary attitude reconstitution can be made in quasi-real time, using a priori star positions with mean errors typically around 0.5 arcsec. After a first run of the three-step reconstitution of the celestial sphere, possibly before the full 2.5 year observation period is completed, considerably more accurate positions are available from which a definitive attitude may be obtained. From available data on gyro drift angles versus time (e.g. Fig. 2.3.5.2 in Aeritalia, 1978, Vol. II) it appears that the first criterion (9.1) is well satisfied by the preliminary attitude, while the second condition (9.2) obviously requires the definitive attitude.

For both reconstitutions we propose to use a fixed-interval smoothing algorithm such as the Square Root Information Smoother (Bierman, 1974, 1977). A smoother is obviously preferable to a filter, because of its higher accuracy with only moderately more computations. The determination of the definitive attitude could in principle be fitted into the set solutions, i.e. by introducing $(\alpha_z \delta_z)$ as unknowns besides the star abscissae, and star mapper and gyro data as additional observations. However, carrying out the attitude reconstitution as a separate task, and taking its output as input ("observations") for the set solutions, appears to have a number of important advantages: the number of unknowns of the set solutions and their complexity are greatly reduced; the same software can be used for both attitude reconstitutions; sophisticated physical models of the attitude motion can relatively easily be implemented with the smoothing formulation, but would be very difficult to incorporate with the set solutions; finally, the attitude reconstitution algorithm can be developed, tested, and run quite independent of other data processing tasks.

The Square Root Information Smoother is derived in Appendix B, to which the reader is referred for more details on notations etc. Basically, the formulation of the attitude reconstitution as a filtering or smoothing problem involves the following components:

- (i) selection of linearized state variables (unknowns), i.e. state vector $\underline{g}$;
- (ii) formulation of the stochastic state transition difference equation (B.1), i.e. transition matrix $\underline{\Phi}$ and process noise covariance $\underline{GG}'$;
- (iii) formulation of normalized observation equations (B.4), i.e. coefficient matrix $\underline{A}$ and observation residuals $\underline{z}$

The selection of state variables is by no means trivial. With increasingly sophisticated models underlying the attitude reconstitution, the number of state variables, $n = \dim(\underline{s})$, tends to grow very rapidly. While the improved models obviously enhance the potential accuracy of the results, the amount of computation increases at least as n^2 , and the algorithms become increasingly sensitive to rounding errors and other numerical instabilities. The simplest model for which the basic requirements (9.1) - (9.2) are met may depend on data which are insufficiently known at present, such as gyro drift rate statistics and the power spectrum of attitude errors.

For illustration we shall consider two models, one which may be considered the minimum model, in which only the attitude angles and drift rates are estimated, and a more elaborate model incorporating the dynamical equations and the attitude control loop.

In both cases the attitude is related to a reference attitude $\underline{a}_{\text{ref}} = (\alpha_{z\text{ref}} \ \delta_{z\text{ref}} \ \omega_{\text{ref}})'$ by means of the residual attitude vector

$$\underline{\chi} = (\phi \ \theta \ \psi)' = \underline{D}_{\text{ref}}(\underline{a} - \underline{a}_{\text{ref}}) \quad (9.3)$$

in which $\underline{a}$ is the true attitude and $\underline{D}_{\text{ref}}$ the (3,3)-matrix similar to $\underline{D}$ in (3.4) but depending on $\delta_{z\text{ref}}$ and ω_{ref} . In the limit of small $|\underline{\chi}|$ it is seen that ϕ , θ , ψ are respectively the rotations about $\underline{x}$, $\underline{y}$, $\underline{z}$ needed to bring $\underline{T}_{\text{ref}}$ into coincidence with $\underline{T}$. The attitude is linearized by this representation to the required accuracy of (say) 0.02 arcsec, provided $|\underline{\chi}|^2 < 10^{-7}$ ($\approx 0.02''$), or $|\underline{\chi}| < 1$ arcmin. The reference attitude should thus be correct to 1 arcmin or better in order that non-linear terms should be negligible. The real-time attitude, having errors of 5 arcsec or less, could of course be taken as reference if it is available at the data processing stage.

Differentiating (9.3) we obtain

$$\underline{T}'\underline{\omega} = \underline{D}\dot{\underline{a}}_{\text{ref}} + \underline{D}\underline{D}_{\text{ref}}^{-1}(\dot{\underline{\chi}} - \dot{\underline{D}}_{\text{ref}}\underline{D}_{\text{ref}}^{-1}\underline{\chi}) \quad (9.4)$$

or to first order, recalling that $\underline{T}'\underline{\omega} \approx (0 \ 0 \ \dot{\omega})'$,

$$\underline{T}'\underline{\omega} - (\underline{T}'\underline{\omega})_{\text{ref}} = \dot{\underline{\chi}} - \underline{\Omega}\underline{\chi}, \quad (9.5)$$

where

$$\underline{\Omega} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \dot{\omega} & 0 \\ -\dot{\omega} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (9.6)$$

In our first model (Model A) the state variables are $\underline{\chi}$, $\dot{\underline{\chi}}$, and $\underline{\Delta b}$, all regarded as functions of time and therefore subscripted j . With

$$\underline{\chi}_{j+1} = \underline{\chi}_j + \dot{\underline{\chi}}_j \delta t \quad (9.7)$$

and $\dot{\underline{\chi}}_j$ modelled as a first-order Markov process analogous to (8.4) - (8.6), we obtain for the state vector $\underline{s} = (\underline{\chi}' \quad \dot{\underline{\chi}}' \quad \underline{\Delta b}')'$ the transition matrix of dimension (10,10) (i.e. $n = 10$)

$$\underline{\Phi} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{I}_3 & \underline{I}_3 \delta t & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{M}_{\dot{\underline{\chi}}} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{M}_b \end{pmatrix} \quad (9.8)$$

and the (10,7)-matrix ($p = 7$)

$$\underline{G} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{0}(3,3) & \underline{0}(3,4) \\ \text{Cov}^{\frac{1}{2}}(\underline{n}_{\dot{\underline{\chi}}}) & \underline{0}(3,4) \\ \underline{0}(4,3) & \text{Cov}^{\frac{1}{2}}(\underline{n}_b) \end{pmatrix} \quad (9.10)$$

where $\underline{0}(q,r)$ or $\underline{0}$ is the null matrix of dimension (q,r), and $\text{Cov}^{\frac{1}{2}}(\underline{n})$ is a square root of the covariance of $\underline{n}$. The time constants and variances of $\dot{\underline{\chi}}$ required for calculation of $\underline{M}_{\dot{\underline{\chi}}}$ and $\text{Cov}(\underline{n}_{\dot{\underline{\chi}}})$ depend e.g. on the attitude control law and the level of disturbing torques, and should be determined by means of realistic simulations of the attitude motion. According to the Aeritalia (1978) study we may have $\tau_{\dot{\underline{\chi}}} \sim 100$ s and $\sigma_{\dot{\underline{\chi}}} \sim 10^{-5}$ rad s⁻¹.

To obtain an observation equation for the gyro readings we compute the reference gyro signal

$$\underline{g}_{j\text{ref}} = \tilde{\underline{K}} (\underline{D}_{\text{ref}} \dot{\underline{a}}_{\text{ref}})_j + \tilde{\underline{b}} \quad (9.11)$$

and obtain, by means of (8.2) and (9.5), the error signal

$$\underline{\Delta g}_j = \underline{g}_j - \underline{g}_{j\text{ref}} = \tilde{\underline{K}} (\dot{\underline{\chi}}_j - \underline{\Omega} \underline{\chi}_j) + \underline{\Delta K} (\underline{D}_{\text{ref}} \dot{\underline{a}}_{\text{ref}})_j + \underline{\Delta b}_j + \underline{v}_j. \quad (9.12)$$

$\underline{\Delta K}$ is not estimated in Model A; however, since $\underline{D}_{\text{ref}} \dot{\underline{a}}_{\text{ref}} = (\underline{T}' \underline{\omega})_{\text{ref}}$ is relatively constant with the adopted mode of scanning, it can be argued that the term containing $\underline{\Delta K}$ is effectively absorbed by $\underline{\Delta b}_j$ and therefore need not be estimated (or even cannot be estimated). With $\underline{C}_v = [\text{Cov}^{\frac{1}{2}}(\underline{v}_j)]^{-1}$ the normalized observation equation (B.4) is given by

$$\underline{A} = (-\underline{C}_v \tilde{\underline{K}} \underline{\Omega} \quad \underline{C}_v \tilde{\underline{K}} \quad \underline{I}_4) \quad (9.13)$$

of dimension (4,10), and the 4-vector

$$\underline{z}_j = \underline{C}_v \underline{\Delta g}_j. \quad (9.14)$$

These equations apply when only gyro data are available. If a star mapper transit occurred in the time interval t_{j-1} to t_j , the matrices $\underline{A}$ and $\underline{z}_j$ must be augmented by a fifth row containing the star mapper observation equation. Let τ be the observed transit time of a star in field f ($=1, 2$) across the central line of one of the two groups of star mapper slits ($g = 1, 2$). From the position of the star, $\underline{E}'\underline{u}$, and the reference attitude, $\underline{E}'\underline{T}_{ref}$, at time τ , field coordinates $(\eta_{ref} \quad \zeta_{ref})'$ are computed by means of (5.1). Now let $\Delta\eta$, $\Delta\zeta$ be the required corrections to η_{ref} , ζ_{ref} , which depend on $\underline{\chi}$ according to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Delta\eta \\ \Delta\zeta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \tan \zeta \cos(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) & \tan \zeta \sin(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) & -1 \\ -\sin(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) & \cos(\eta \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma) & 0 \end{pmatrix} \underline{\chi} \quad (9.15)$$

Since the equation (4.4) of the central line is known a priori, we have the equation

$$\eta_{ref} + \Delta\eta = \tilde{\eta}_{fg}(\zeta_{ref} + \Delta\zeta) \approx \tilde{\eta}_{fg}(\zeta_{ref}) + \Delta\zeta \tilde{\eta}'_{fg}(\zeta_{ref}), \quad (9.16)$$

where $\tilde{\eta}'_{fg} = (d/d\zeta)\tilde{\eta}_{fg}$. Combining with (9.15) we find the observation equation

$$\underline{B}_{fg}(\zeta_{ref}) \underline{\chi} = \tilde{\eta}_{fg}(\zeta_{ref}) - \eta_{ref} \quad (9.17)$$

where

$$\underline{B}_{fg}(\zeta) = \begin{pmatrix} \tan \zeta \cos[\tilde{\eta}_{fg}(\zeta) \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma] + \tilde{\eta}'_{fg}(\zeta) \sin[\tilde{\eta}_{fg}(\zeta) \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma] \\ \tan \zeta \sin[\tilde{\eta}_{fg}(\zeta) \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma] - \tilde{\eta}'_{fg}(\zeta) \cos[\tilde{\eta}_{fg}(\zeta) \pm \frac{1}{2}\gamma] \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9.18)$$

is a vector depending only on ζ and indices f and g (remember that upper/lower sign refers to $f = 1/2$). If σ_τ is the estimated mean error of the observed transit time and σ_p the positional error of the star, the normalized observation equation is obtained by multiplying (9.17) with $[\sigma_p^2 + (\sigma_\tau \dot{\omega})^2]^{-\frac{1}{2}}$.

A serious drawback of the above model is that the resultant torque acting on the satellite (or, equivalently, $\ddot{\underline{X}}$) is effectively regarded as unpredictable and uncorrelated (white) noise. It neglects the presence of torques (such as solar radiation pressure) having long correlation times as well as the fact that a large fraction of the total torque is in fact predictable from the dynamical equations and environmental conditions, or even intentionally exerted by the attitude control system. One way to take these factors into account would be to model $\ddot{\underline{X}}$ (rather than $\dot{\underline{X}}$) as a Markov process, and to introduce regular observations of $\ddot{\underline{X}}$ in the form of a priori estimates calculated from predicted torques and the dynamical equations. This leads to the following Model B.

Let us first derive the dynamical equations, i.e. the equations of motion expressed in body coordinates (with respect to $\underline{T}$). The satellite is regarded as a rigid body, except for the presence of reaction wheels. Let $\underline{J}$, $\underline{h}$, and $\underline{e}$ be respectively the moment-of-inertia tensor of the satellite, the angular momentum of the wheels, and the external torque. The total angular momentum of the satellite is $\underline{J}\underline{\omega} + \underline{h}$. With respect to an inertial frame such as $\underline{E}$, the equation of motion is $(d/dt)[\underline{E}'(\underline{J}\underline{\omega} + \underline{h})] = \underline{E}'\underline{e}$, or

$$\frac{d}{dt} [(\underline{E}'\underline{J}\underline{E})(\underline{E}'\underline{\omega}) + \underline{E}'\underline{h}] = \underline{E}'\underline{e}. \quad (9.19)$$

Transforming to the rotating telescope system $\underline{T}$, and using the identities $\dot{\underline{E}} = \underline{0}$ (inertial), $(d/dt)(\underline{T}'\underline{J}\underline{T}) = \underline{0}$ (inertia tensor in telescope coordinates), and $\underline{T}'\dot{\underline{T}} = \underline{T}'\underline{\omega} \wedge \underline{T} = (\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}) \wedge$ [eqn (A.7)], we obtain

$$(\underline{T}'\underline{J}\underline{T}) \frac{d}{dt} (\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}) = - \frac{d}{dt} (\underline{T}'\underline{h}) - (\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}) \wedge [(\underline{T}'\underline{J}\underline{T})(\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}) + \underline{T}'\underline{h}] + \underline{T}'\underline{e}. \quad (9.20)$$

$-(d/dt)(\underline{T}'\underline{h})$ is the apparent torque exerted on the satellite by accelerating the reaction wheels, and is approximately known from the attitude control commands (which, if they are not directly available, can be exactly reproduced by running the real-time attitude determination and control programs on ground). The wheels speeds $(\underline{T}'\underline{h})$ are similarly known. The external torque $\underline{T}'\underline{e}$ is at least partly predictable. Thus we are able to compute an estimate of the total (apparent) torque

$$\underline{f} = - \frac{d}{dt} (\underline{T}'\underline{h}) - (\underline{T}'\underline{\omega})_{\text{ref}} \wedge [(\underline{T}'\underline{J}\underline{T})(\underline{T}'\underline{\omega})_{\text{ref}} + \underline{T}'\underline{h}] + (\underline{T}'\underline{e}). \quad (9.21)$$

By means of (9.5) we obtain an observation equation for $\ddot{\underline{X}}$ and $\dot{\underline{X}}$,

$$(\underline{T}'\underline{J}\underline{T}) \ddot{\underline{X}}_j - (\underline{T}'\underline{J}\underline{T}) \underline{\Omega} \dot{\underline{X}}_j = \underline{f}_j + \underline{n}_{fj} \quad (9.22)$$

where the noise term $\underline{n}_{fj}$ accounts for estimation errors of the various terms in (9.21). Note that, depending on the time constant of $\ddot{\underline{X}}$, this observation equation need not be included at every time step; ideally, the interval between observations should be just large enough for the estimation errors to be essentially uncorrelated.

For the state vector $\underline{s} = (\underline{X}' \ \dot{\underline{X}}' \ \ddot{\underline{X}}' \ \Delta b')'$ the transition matrix becomes ($n = 13$)

$$\underline{\Phi} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{I}_3 & \underline{I}_3 \delta t & \frac{1}{2} \underline{I}_3 \delta t^2 & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{I}_3 & \underline{I}_3 \delta t & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{M}_{\ddot{\underline{X}}} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{M}_b \end{pmatrix} \quad (9.23)$$

and ($p = 7$)

$$\underline{G} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{0} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} \\ \text{Cov}^{\frac{1}{2}}(\underline{n}_{\ddot{\underline{X}}}) & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \text{Cov}^{\frac{1}{2}}(\underline{n}_b) \end{pmatrix} \quad (9.24)$$

The observation equation matrices $\underline{A}$ and $\underline{z}$ remain the same as in Model A, except that (9.22), normalized, is appended at regular intervals.

10. IDT DATA PROCESSING

The processing of IDT data will be based on the signal model (6.4), valid for single stars, with $m = 2$ harmonics. Since any more complex image (multiple star, extended object, defocussed or otherwise aberrated image) will give an intensity modulation which can be regarded as a superposition of elementary signals of the form of (6.4), it follows that a completely general model requires five signal parameters, e.g. the Fourier coefficients of the series $a_0 + a_1 \cos(2\pi\tilde{G}_k) + b_1 \sin(2\pi\tilde{G}_k) + a_2 \cos(4\pi\tilde{G}_k) + b_2 \sin(4\pi\tilde{G}_k)$, where $\tilde{G}_k$ is a reference grid coordinate. As explained later, it is however advantageous to choose a slightly different definition of parameters, such as $\underline{b}$ in the formula

$$E(N_k) = I_k(\underline{b}) = b_1 + b_2 \cos(H_k + b_3) + b_4 \cos(2H_k + 2b_3) + b_5 \sin(2H_k + 2b_3), \quad (10.1)$$

where $H_k = 2\pi\tilde{G}_k$ is a reference modulation phase calculated from the a priori grid coordinate ($\tilde{G}_k$) corresponding to the a priori star position and preliminary attitude data.

The parameters b_i will of course in reality fluctuate somewhat over various time scales. A necessary assumption is that these fluctuations are small enough over a limited stretch of data that application of our model results in the determination of meaningful average parameter values. This assumption is very difficult to quantify without numerical experimentation, but it is felt that amplitude variations of the order of 10 % (of b_1, b_2, b_4, b_5) and phase fluctuations of the order of 0.1 modulation period (for b_3) could be tolerated. The latter requirement imposes a constraint on the attitude rate error, eqn (9.1).

Given a set of pulse counts $\{N_k\}$ collected on a particular star in a 2 sec interval (say), and the corresponding set of reference modulation phases $\{H_k\}$, estimation of the parameter vector $\underline{b} = (b_1 \ b_2 \ b_3 \ b_4 \ b_5)'$ follows the maximum likelihood method. Assuming Poisson distribution of counts, (6.1), the log likelihood function is

$$\ell(\underline{b}) = \sum_k [-\ln(N_k!) + N_k \ln I_k(\underline{b}) - I_k(\underline{b})]. \quad (10.2)$$

Putting

$$v_i(\underline{b}) = \sum_k \left[\frac{N_k}{I_k(\underline{b})} - 1 \right] \frac{\partial I_k}{\partial b_i}; \quad \underline{v} = (v_1 \ v_2 \ v_3 \ v_4 \ v_5)', \quad (10.3)$$

the maximum likelihood equations $\underline{v}(\underline{b}) = \underline{0}$ are solved by a Newton-Raphson type iteration,

$$\underline{b}^{(r+1)} = \underline{b}^{(r)} + \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{v}^{(r)}, \quad (10.4)$$

where $\underline{F}$ is the information matrix with elements

$$F_{ij} = \sum_k \frac{1}{I_k(\hat{\underline{b}})} \frac{\partial I_k}{\partial b_i} \frac{\partial I_k}{\partial b_j} \quad (10.5)$$

As a first approximation $\hat{\underline{b}}$ may be obtained by conventional Fourier analysis of the pulse counts (i.e. by unweighted least-squares estimation of the Fourier coefficients). After the first iteration $\underline{F}$ need not be recomputed. $\underline{F}^{-1}$ is of course also the covariance of the ML estimate. A procedure for calculation of the ML estimate $\hat{\underline{b}}$ and its covariance has been given elsewhere and is not repeated here (Lindgren, 1980-02-22).

The five parameters b_i are thus estimated under the assumption of no prior information on their values or internal relations. This will not be true e.g. if we are certain that the object observed is a point source and calibration values of M_1 , M_2 and v_2 are at hand. In this case there are only three degrees of freedom, corresponding e.g. to the three parameters B , I_0 and $\Delta G = G_k - \tilde{G}_k$. From (6.4) and (10.1) we find the following relations for a single star:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} b_1 &= (B + I_0) \Delta t \\ b_2 &= M_1 I_0 \Delta t \\ b_3 &= 2\pi \Delta G \\ b_4 &= M_2 I_0 \Delta t \cos v_2 \\ b_5 &= M_2 I_0 \Delta t \sin v_2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10.6)$$

It is seen that knowledge of M_1 , M_2 , v_2 imposes constraints on b_2 , b_4 and b_5 , since $b_4/b_2 = (M_2/M_1) \cos v_2$ and $b_5/b_2 = (M_2/M_1) \sin v_2$ are supposed to be known. This can also be written in the form of two linear constraints,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (M_2/M_1) b_2 - (\cos v_2) b_4 - (\sin v_2) b_5 &= 0 \\ (\sin v_2) b_4 - (\cos v_2) b_5 &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \Leftrightarrow \underline{C} \underline{b} = \underline{0}, \quad (10.7)$$

where $\underline{C}$ is a (2,5) matrix of known coefficients. The ML estimate of $\underline{b}$ satisfying (10.7) is obtained by maximizing the modified log likelihood function

$$\ell(\underline{b}, \underline{\lambda}) = \ell(\underline{b}) - \underline{\lambda}' \underline{C} \underline{b}, \quad (10.8)$$

where $\underline{\lambda} = (\lambda_1 \ \lambda_2)'$ is a vector of Lagrangian multipliers.

It is possible to avoid going back to the original log likelihood (10.2) depending on individual counts, by noting that it is unlikely, if our model (6.4) is correct, that the unconstrained ML estimate $\hat{\underline{b}}$ is very far from the

true vector (or the constrained estimate of it), if the "distance" is measured in relation to the covariance of the unconstrained solution $\underline{F}^{-1}$. In other words, a quadratic expansion of the unconstrained log likelihood around the maximum,

$$\ell(\underline{b}) \approx \ell(\hat{\underline{b}}) - \frac{1}{2}(\underline{b} - \hat{\underline{b}})' \underline{F} (\underline{b} - \hat{\underline{b}}), \quad (10.9)$$

is quite adequate over the region of interest, simply because it is improbable that the loss, $\ell(\underline{b}) - \ell(\hat{\underline{b}})$, is much greater than unity so that higher-order terms would be important.

Introducing the approximation (10.9) into (10.8) we obtain an explicit formula for the constrained solution,

$$\underline{b} = \hat{\underline{b}} - \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{C}' (\underline{C} \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{C}')^{-1} \underline{C} \hat{\underline{b}}. \quad (10.10)$$

Defining the signal parameters as in (10.1), rather than as conventional Fourier coefficients, has the important advantage that the single star constraints are linear, hence the simple expression for the constrained solution.

Thanks to (10.9) it is generally true that all relevant information is contained in the unconstrained estimate $\hat{\underline{b}}$ and its covariance $\underline{F}^{-1}$, also when deviations from the unconstrained formulation (10.1) are considered. Computation of $\hat{\underline{b}}$ and $\underline{F}^{-1}$ would therefore be a useful way to compress the raw count data without significant loss of information.

Using a constraint like (10.7) is of course motivated only when the quality of the exterior information (in this case, M_2/M_1 and v_2) is very much better than what could be derived from the observation itself. This will be the case for the faintest stars. In other cases it may be necessary to allow some flexibility corresponding to the uncertainty of calibration data. This feature is perhaps most easily introduced by defining a new parameter vector, $\underline{\beta}$, with $\beta_i = b_i$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $\beta_4 = b_4/b_2$, $\beta_5 = b_5/b_2$. Then

$$I_k(\underline{\beta}) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 [\cos(H_k + \beta_3) + \beta_4 \cos(2H_k + 2\beta_3) + \beta_5 \sin(2H_k + 2\beta_3)]. \quad (10.11)$$

The unconstrained ML estimate of $\underline{\beta}$ is of course given by $\hat{\beta}_1 = \hat{b}_1$, ..., $\hat{\beta}_5 = \hat{b}_5/\hat{b}_2$ and its covariance is

$$\underline{\Phi}^{-1} = \underline{B} \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{B}', \quad (10.12)$$

where $\underline{B}$ is the partial derivatives matrix, $B_{ij} = \partial \beta_i / \partial b_j$. Now let $\tilde{\beta}_4, \tilde{\beta}_5$ be calibration values for $(M_2/M_1) \cos v_2$ and $(M_2/M_1) \sin v_2$, respectively, and let $\underline{G}$ be the covariance matrix representing the uncertainty of the calibration values. The a priori likelihood of any given parameter vector is approximated

by a bivariate Gaussian, $\text{lik}(\underline{\beta}) = (2\pi)^{-1} |\underline{G}|^{-1/2} \exp[-\frac{1}{2}(\underline{\beta} - \underline{\hat{\beta}})' \underline{G}^{-1} (\underline{\beta} - \underline{\hat{\beta}})]$. Note that $\underline{G}^{-1}$ can be augmented by zeroes to yield a (5,5) matrix. The total likelihood, given both observation and calibration, becomes

$$\ell(\underline{\beta}) = \text{const.} - \frac{1}{2}(\underline{\beta} - \underline{\hat{\beta}})' \underline{\Phi} (\underline{\beta} - \underline{\hat{\beta}}) - \frac{1}{2}(\underline{\beta} - \underline{\tilde{\beta}})' \underline{G}^{-1} (\underline{\beta} - \underline{\tilde{\beta}}). \quad (10.13)$$

The maximizing vector is

$$\underline{\beta} = (\underline{\Phi} + \underline{G}^{-1})^{-1} (\underline{\Phi} \underline{\hat{\beta}} + \underline{G}^{-1} \underline{\tilde{\beta}}). \quad (10.14)$$

Still other formulations than (10.1) and (10.11) are of course possible. They are in principle equivalent as long as the Jacobian of the transformation from $\underline{b}$ to the alternative parameter vectors is different from zero. The final choice of parameters may rather be a matter of computational convenience. For consistency we shall use formulation (10.1) in the sequel.

Calculation of compressed data, e.g. $\underline{b}$ and $\underline{F}^{-1}$, requires a uniquely defined set of reference modulation phases $\{H_k\}$; $H_k = 2\pi \tilde{G}_k$. Computation of $\tilde{G}_k$ is based on the following data:

(i) the a priori direction to the star at the moment of observation (t_k), i.e. $\underline{E}'\underline{u}$. This must be exactly computable from Input Catalogue data and orbital data, according to the precepts of Section 2;

(ii) an agreed-upon preliminary attitude, satisfying (9.1); and

(iii) the a priori transformation from field coordinates to G, i.e. the table of small scale distortion, $\delta G(\eta, \zeta)$ and coefficients $\tilde{G}_{fkl}$, cf. (4.3).

Rigorous computation of $\tilde{G}_k$ for every IDT sample is neither practicable nor necessary. It is probably sufficient to compute, by rigorous transformations, the field coordinates $(\tilde{\eta} \ \tilde{\zeta})$ once per star and 2 sec interval (say, at time t_k); then interpolate field coordinates in proportion to

$$\int_{t_k}^{t_k} \hat{z}' \hat{\omega} dt \approx \hat{\omega}_k - \hat{\omega}_k + (\hat{\alpha}_{zk} - \hat{\alpha}_{zk}) \sin \hat{\delta}_{zk} \quad (10.15)$$

[cf. eqn (3.4)], where $(\hat{\alpha}_z \ \hat{\delta}_z \ \hat{\omega})$ is the preliminary attitude; and finally apply the a priori transformation from field coordinate to $\tilde{G}$.

11. SET SOLUTIONS (STEP 1)

The net result of the IDT data processing will be the determination of $\Delta G = G_k - \tilde{G}_k$ for the different stars observed in an interval of a few seconds of time, during which ΔG is assumed to be constant. Thanks to the interlacing of observations it will be possible to refer measurements of ΔG on several stars to the same instant (t_k), thus constituting a frame. The purpose of this concept is to group observations affected by virtually the same attitude errors [z'_ϵ and Δz in (5.8)], so that these can be immediately eliminated while accumulating the normal equations for the set solution.

The assembly of observations collected in a time interval of about 12 h will be called a set. During such an interval the nominal spin axis ($\underline{z}$) will change its direction by an angle $\lesssim 3^\circ$. Positions of stars in a set will be expressed in a coordinate system $\underline{R} = (\underline{x}_R \ \underline{y}_R \ \underline{z}_R)$ which is exactly defined in relation to $\underline{E}$ by means of two angles α_r, δ_r . A triad of unit vectors aligned with $\underline{E}$ will become $\underline{R}$ after two rotations:

- (i) by an angle $\alpha_r + \frac{1}{2}\pi$ about the original z axis; and
- (ii) by an angle $\frac{1}{2}\pi - \delta_r$ about the resulting x axis.

Thus,

$$\underline{R}'\underline{E} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \alpha_r & \cos \alpha_r & 0 \\ -\sin \delta_r \cos \alpha_r & -\sin \delta_r \sin \alpha_r & \cos \delta_r \\ \cos \delta_r \cos \alpha_r & \cos \delta_r \sin \alpha_r & \sin \delta_r \end{pmatrix} \quad (11.1)$$

Polar coordinates in $\underline{R}$ are called abscissa (ν) and ordinate (ρ); for a star in direction of unit vector $\underline{u}$ they are given by

$$\underline{R}'\underline{u} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \rho \cos \nu \\ \cos \rho \sin \nu \\ \sin \rho \end{pmatrix} \quad (11.2)$$

$(\alpha_r \ \delta_r)$ is thus the celestial position of $\underline{z}_R$, corresponding to $\rho = \frac{1}{2}\pi$. It is also the pole of the reference great circle (RGC) of the set. The intersection of this circle with the equator, at right ascension $\alpha_r + \frac{1}{2}\pi$, defines $\underline{x}_R$ and the origin of abscissae ($\nu = 0, \rho = 0$). Finally $\underline{y}_R = \underline{z}_R \wedge \underline{x}_R$ is also on the RGC, at $\nu = \frac{1}{2}\pi, \rho = 0$.

The solution of a set depends on writing ΔG as a combination of corrections to the star position (in relation to $\underline{R}$, viz. $\Delta\nu, \Delta\rho$), the average attitude corrections of the frame ($\Delta\alpha_z, \Delta\delta_z, \Delta\omega$), and corrections to the various instrument parameters ($\Delta G_{fkl} = G_{fkl} - \tilde{G}_{fkl}, \Delta\gamma$, etc.).

Differentiating (4.3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G &= \sum_{k,l} \tilde{\eta}^k \tilde{\zeta}^l \Delta G_{fkl} + \left[\sum_{k,l} k \tilde{G}_{fkl} \tilde{\eta}^{k-1} \tilde{\zeta}^l \right] \Delta \eta + \left[\sum_{k,l} l \tilde{G}_{fkl} \tilde{\eta}^k \tilde{\zeta}^{l-1} \right] \Delta \zeta \\ &= \sum_{k,l} \eta^k \zeta^l \Delta G_{fkl} + a(\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta}) \Delta \eta + b(\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta}) \Delta \zeta, \end{aligned} \quad (11.3)$$

where $(\tilde{\eta}, \tilde{\zeta})$ are a priori field coordinates defined as in Section 10 and referred to the common epoch (t_k) of the frame. It should be noted that $|b| \ll |a|$ since the slits are very nearly perpendicular to the η axis.

$\Delta \eta = \eta - \tilde{\eta}$ and $\Delta \zeta = \zeta - \tilde{\zeta}$ are given by (5.8) and (5.3), which for the set solution must be rewritten with $\underline{\Delta u}$ expressed in terms of Δu , $\Delta \rho$ and $\underline{\Delta z}$ in terms of $\Delta \alpha_z$, $\Delta \delta_z$, $\Delta \omega$. From (11.2) we find by differentiation

$$\underline{R}' \underline{\Delta u} = \underline{U}_r \begin{pmatrix} \Delta u \\ \Delta \rho \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11.4)$$

where

$$\underline{U}_r = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos \rho \sin \nu & -\sin \rho \cos \nu \\ \cos \rho \cos \nu & -\sin \rho \sin \nu \\ 0 & \cos \rho \end{pmatrix}. \quad (11.5)$$

Similarly

$$\underline{E}' \underline{\Delta z} = \underline{U}_e \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \alpha_z \\ \Delta \delta_z \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11.6)$$

where $\underline{U}_e$ is obtained from $\underline{U}_r$ by putting $\rho := \delta_z$, $\nu := \alpha_z$. Moreover, in analogy with (3.4) we have $\underline{T}' \underline{\varepsilon} = \underline{D}(\Delta \alpha_z \quad \Delta \delta_z \quad \Delta \omega)'$ from which

$$\underline{z}' \underline{\varepsilon} = \Delta \alpha_z \sin \delta_z + \Delta \omega. \quad (11.7)$$

Inserting (5.8) and (5.3) into (11.3) and using (11.4) - (11.7) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G &= \sum_k \sum_l \tilde{\eta}^k \tilde{\zeta}^l \Delta G_{fkl} - a(\Delta \alpha_z \sin \delta_z + \Delta \omega) \mp \frac{1}{2} a \Delta \gamma + \\ &+ \sec \zeta \left\{ a \sec \zeta [(\underline{R}' \underline{z}) \wedge (\underline{R}' \underline{u})]' + b(\underline{R}' \underline{z})' \right\} \underline{U}_r \begin{pmatrix} \Delta u \\ \Delta \rho \end{pmatrix} + \\ &+ \sec \zeta \left\{ -a \tan \zeta [(\underline{E}' \underline{z}) \wedge (\underline{E}' \underline{u})]' + b(\underline{E}' \underline{u})' \right\} \underline{U}_e \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \alpha_z \\ \Delta \delta_z \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (11.8)$$

The correction to the nominal basic angle, $\Delta\gamma$, can obviously be absorbed by a simple redefinition of the distortion coefficients,

$$\Delta G_{fkl} := \Delta G_{fkl} + (-)^f \frac{1}{2} (k+1) \tilde{G}_{f(k+1)l} \Delta\gamma, \quad (11.9)$$

whereby it is convenient to regard the value γ in (5.1) etc as a postulated angle, while the true basic angle is defined only via the coefficients G_{fkl} .

Equation (11.8) will be used as an observation equation with ΔG_{fkl} , $\Delta\omega$, and $(\Delta\alpha_z \sin \delta_z + \Delta\omega)$ as the only unknowns. This is possible only because the coefficients of the remaining corrections, $\Delta\rho$, $\Delta\alpha_z$, and $\Delta\delta_z$, are relatively much smaller. To see this let us write $\underline{R}'z = (r_x \ r_y \ r_z)'$, where $|r_x|$, $|r_y| \ll 1$ and $|r_z| \approx 1$ since $(\alpha_r \ \delta_r)$ is close to $(\alpha_z \ \delta_z)$ or $(\alpha_z + \pi \ -\delta_z)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [(\underline{R}'z) \wedge (\underline{R}'u)]' \underline{U}_r \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\omega \\ \Delta\rho \end{pmatrix} &= (-r_x \sin \rho \cos \nu - r_y \sin \rho \sin \nu + r_z \cos \rho) \cos \rho \Delta\omega + \\ &+ (r_x \sin \nu - r_y \cos \nu) \Delta\rho. \end{aligned} \quad (11.10)$$

From this it is clear that the coefficient for $\Delta\omega$ is of the order of $|a|$ while that for $\Delta\rho$ is of the order of $|r_{x,y}/r_z| \cdot |a| + |b| \ll |a|$. The coefficients for $\Delta\alpha_z$ and $\Delta\delta_z$ are of the order of $|a \tan \zeta| + |b| \ll |a|$ since $|\zeta| \ll 1$. In principle these terms could be computed according to (11.8) and subtracted from ΔG to yield the observation equation; however it may be better to make a rigorous computation of ΔG from updated unknowns and take the difference from the observed value ($\Delta\Delta G = O-C$ in ΔG) as left-hand side. Then $\Delta\rho$, $\Delta\alpha_z$ and $\Delta\delta_z$ are simply set = 0. It may also be advantageous to split the distortion coefficients G_{fkl} into components equal and different between the two fields ($f = 1, 2$), e.g.

$$G_{fkl} = g_{kl} - (-)^f h_{kl}. \quad (11.11)$$

Introducing finally $\overline{\Delta\omega} = \Delta\omega + \Delta\alpha_z \sin \delta_z$ we have the observation equation

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\Delta G &= \sum_k \sum_l \tilde{\eta}^k \tilde{\zeta}^l [\Delta g_{kl} - (-)^f \Delta h_{kl}] - a(\tilde{\eta} \ \tilde{\zeta}) \overline{\Delta\omega} + \\ &+ \sec \tilde{\zeta} \cos \rho \left\{ a(\tilde{\eta} \ \tilde{\zeta}) \sec \tilde{\zeta} (-r_x \sin \rho \cos \nu - r_y \sin \rho \sin \nu + r_z \cos \rho) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + b(\tilde{\eta} \ \tilde{\zeta}) (-r_x \sin \nu + r_y \cos \nu) \right\} \Delta\Delta\omega. \end{aligned} \quad (11.12)$$

The attitude error about the z axis, $\underline{z}'\underline{\varepsilon} = \overline{\Delta\omega}$ is the same for all observations referred to the same frame epoch and may be eliminated immediately upon

forming the normal equations. Thus only Δv_i (i = star index number) and $\Delta g_{k\ell}$, $\Delta h_{k\ell}$ are left as unknowns. With an areal density of 2.4 stars deg^{-2} the number of stars in a set is about 1800. Due to the undefined abscissa zero point the normal equations will have a rank deficiency = 1 but can be solved by one of several methods (cf. Appendix D).

The result of a set solution (for set #j) will be the independently determined distortion coefficients $g_{k\ell}$, $h_{k\ell}$ and the abscissa corrections Δv_i for all the stars in the set ($\forall i: i \in S_j$). The abscissa corrections Δv_i should be interpreted as follows. Let $\underline{r}_j$ be the pole of the reference great circle for the set, $\underline{u}_i$ the satellitocentric coordinate direction to the star, $\underline{u}_i^{\text{cat}}$ the corresponding catalogue (a priori) star direction, and $\Delta \underline{u}_i = \underline{u}_i - \underline{u}_i^{\text{cat}}$ the required correction to the catalogue direction. Then $\Delta v_i + c_j$ is the angular measure of $\Delta \underline{u}_i$ as viewed from the tip of $\underline{r}_j$, c_j being the common zero point correction for the set. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta v_i + c_j &\approx \sin(\Delta v_i + c_j) = |(\underline{r}_j \wedge \underline{u}_i^{\text{cat}}) \wedge (\underline{r}_j \wedge \underline{u}_i)| \cdot |\underline{r}_j \wedge \underline{u}_i^{\text{cat}}|^{-1} |\underline{r}_j \wedge \underline{u}_i|^{-1} \\ &\approx \sec^2 \rho_i (\underline{r}_j \wedge \underline{u}_i^{\text{cat}})' \Delta \underline{u}_i \end{aligned} \quad (11.13)$$

Due to bad Input Catalogue positions it will quite often happen that the a priori grid coordinate $\tilde{G}_k$ differs from the true (or observed) grid coordinate by more than ± 0.5 grid period. In that case the grid coordinate derived from the observation will probably be wrong by an integer number of grid periods. Since one grid period always corresponds to very nearly the same angle on the sky, and since the instantaneous scan direction is never much inclined with respect to the reference great circle, the derived abscissa correction for this star will similarly be wrong by a multiple of the grid period $1/\langle a \rangle \approx 1.1$ arc-sec. For multiple stars it will also happen that the effective photocentre (as observed with the periodic grid, which is generally not the barycentre of the light distribution) is displaced by an unknown amount; but since the displacement will be very nearly the same for all the scans in a set this will merely cause a similar shift of the abscissa correction. Thus stars with bad initial positions and multiple stars will usually not show up as discordant observations in the set solution. Moreover the results, in terms of distortion coefficients and abscissa corrections for single stars with good initial positions, will not be deteriorated by the inclusion of 'bad' stars. This is essential for the formation of a network of Primary Reference Stars as the next step of the data analysis.

12. PRIMARY REFERENCE STARS SOLUTION (STEP 2)

In order to derive the set zero point correction c_j , it is in principle sufficient to know the accurate astrometric parameters for one single star observed in the set. The right member of (11.13) can then be computed and c_j obtained by subtracting the 'observed' relative abscissa correction Δu_{ji} . (Note the added subscript j indicating the set to which the abscissa correction belongs.) The resulting uncertainty of c_j would be practically equal to the uncertainty of Δu_{ji} and would then significantly add to the uncertainties of the other relative abscissa corrections when forming the absolute corrections $\Delta u_{ji} + c_j$. The zero point uncertainty can however be made relatively unimportant if it is derived from some 10 to 20 stars per set rather than from one star only. This requires that accurate astrometric parameters are known for a subset of about 1000 programme stars. These Primary Reference Stars (PRS) should be selected according to given criteria, the most important being: no sign of multiplicity; good observing history within the mission; good sky distribution; preferably not too faint. FK5 stars are obvious candidates, but the final choice of PRS can only be made after completion of the mission when all multiplicity indicators have been reviewed.

The PRS astrometric parameters $(\alpha_o, \delta_o, \mu_\alpha, \mu_\delta, \tilde{\omega})_i$ are obtained from a least-squares solution with Δu_{ji} as observables (right-hand sides) in the following way. From (2.6) and (2.5) we obtain by differentiation

$$\Delta \tilde{u} = \Delta u_o + \tau \Delta \tilde{u}_o + (\underline{I} - \underline{u}_o \underline{u}_o') \rho_o \Delta \tilde{\omega} \quad (12.1)$$

(using some obvious approximations). Using (2.3) and (2.4) we have then

$$\begin{aligned} (\underline{r} \wedge \underline{u}_o)' \Delta \tilde{u} &= [\underline{E}'(\underline{r} \wedge \underline{u}_o)]' (\underline{E}' \Delta \tilde{u}) = \\ &= [(\underline{E}' \underline{r}) \wedge (\underline{E}' \underline{u}_o)]' \left[\underline{u}_o \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \alpha_o \\ \Delta \delta_o \end{pmatrix} + \tau \underline{u}_o \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \mu_\alpha \\ \Delta \mu_\delta \end{pmatrix} + \underline{E}' \rho_o \Delta \tilde{\omega} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (12.2)$$

where

$$\underline{u}_o = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos \delta_o \sin \alpha_o & -\sin \delta_o \cos \alpha_o \\ \cos \delta_o \cos \alpha_o & -\sin \delta_o \sin \alpha_o \\ 0 & \cos \delta_o \end{pmatrix} \quad (12.3)$$

[cf. (11.5)] and we have used that $(\underline{r} \wedge \underline{u})'(\underline{I} - \underline{u}\underline{u}') = (\underline{r} \wedge \underline{u})'$. Expressing $\underline{E}' \underline{r}$ and $\underline{E}' \underline{u}_o$ in terms of (α_r, δ_r) and (α_o, δ_o) respectively, and putting $\underline{E}' \rho_o = \rho_o (\cos \delta_b \cos \alpha_b \quad \cos \delta_b \sin \alpha_b \quad \sin \delta_b)'$ (α_b, δ_b being satellitocentric coordinates of the Solar System barycentre), we find

$$[(\tilde{E}'_r) \wedge (\tilde{E}'_{u_0})]' \tilde{u}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} [\cos \delta_o \sin \delta_r - \sin \delta_o \cos \delta_r \cos(\alpha_o - \alpha_r)] \cos \delta_o \\ \sin \delta_r \sin(\alpha_o - \alpha_r) \end{pmatrix}' \quad (12.4)$$

and

$$[(\tilde{E}'_r) \wedge (\tilde{E}'_{u_0})]' (\tilde{E}'_{\rho_0}) = \rho_0 [\sin \delta_o \cos \delta_r \cos \delta_b \sin(\alpha_r - \alpha_b) + \sin \delta_r \cos \delta_b \cos \delta_o \sin(\alpha_b - \alpha_o) + \sin \delta_b \cos \delta_o \cos \delta_r \sin(\alpha_o - \alpha_r)]. \quad (12.5)$$

The observation equation for the corrections to the PRS astrometric parameters can thus be written

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cos \delta_o \sin \delta_r - \sin \delta_o \cos \delta_r \cos(\alpha_o - \alpha_r) \\ \sin \delta_r \sin(\alpha_o - \alpha_r) \\ \tau [\cos \delta_o \sin \delta_r - \sin \delta_o \cos \delta_r \cos(\alpha_o - \alpha_r)] \\ \tau [\sin \delta_r \sin(\alpha_o - \alpha_r)] \\ (\tilde{r} \wedge \tilde{u}_0)' \rho_0 \end{pmatrix}'_i \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \alpha_o \cos \delta_o \\ \Delta \delta_o \\ \Delta \mu_\alpha \cos \delta_o \\ \Delta \mu_\delta \\ \Delta \tilde{\omega} \end{pmatrix}'_i \sec^2 \rho_{ji} - c_j = \Delta u_{ji} \quad (12.6)$$

When accumulating the normal equations for the ~5000 PRS parameters, the set zero point corrections c_j are successively eliminated in the same way as $\overline{\Delta \omega}$ for the set solutions. Thus the resulting system of normal equations will have about 5000 unknowns and a rank deficiency of 6, due to the undefined orientation and rotation of the coordinate system. If $\Delta \alpha_o$, $\Delta \delta_o$, $\Delta \mu_\alpha$, and $\Delta \mu_\delta$ in (12.6) are interpreted as corrections to positions and proper motions in the FK5 system, it is natural to adopt the generalized (Moore-Penrose) solution for a provisional Hipparcos system. This will minimize the (weighted) sum of $(\Delta \alpha_o \cos \delta_o)^2 + (\Delta \delta_o)^2 + (\Delta \mu_\alpha \cos \delta_o)^2 + (\Delta \mu_\delta)^2$ over the PRS, which seems to be a reasonable way to fix (provisionally) the system orientation and rotation. An algorithm for the generalized solution is given in Appendix D.

13. BACK SUBSTITUTION (STEP 3)

In addition to the PRS astrometric parameters the Step 2 solution yields abscissa zero point corrections c_j in a coordinate system provisionally adapted to FK5. The observation equations for the astrometric parameters of the remaining 99 % programme stars are identical to (12.6), except that c_j are moved to the right members, thus using the absolute abscissa corrections $\Delta T_{ji} = \Delta v_{ji} + c_j$ as observables. Since no two stars have a common unknown, the normal equations can be formed and solved independently for one star at a time, thus involving linear systems with only five unknowns.

A given star is typically observed in about 25 different sets. Thanks to this redundancy of observations, a study of absolute abscissa residuals, $\Delta T_{ji} - \hat{\Delta T}_{ji}$ (where $\hat{\Delta T}_{ji}$ is the fitted observable, i.e. the left-hand member of the observation equation), will be extremely valuable for resolving slit ambiguities, detecting multiplicity, and eliminating spurious abscissa measurements. Slit ambiguity is likely to cause large residuals and will occur when the Input Catalogue position is wrong by more than about 0.6 arcsec (as will probably be the case for every other programme star). It is then necessary to correct the observed ΔT_{ji} by small integer multiples of the average grid period, s , until acceptable residuals are obtained. This can be judged e.g. from the conventional chi-square

$$\chi^2 = \sum_j \sigma_{ji}^{-2} (\Delta T_{ji} - \hat{\Delta T}_{ji})^2, \quad (13.1)$$

where the abscissa variances $\sigma_{ji}^2 = \text{Var}(\Delta T_{ji})$ are independently estimated from the set and PRS solutions.

Several techniques could be tried in order to resolve slit ambiguities. Perhaps the most direct approach would be based on inspection of individual residuals e.g. according to the following algorithm. Correct the observation with the numerically largest residual by $+s$ or $-s$, depending on the sign of the residual; then make a new least-squares solution for the astrometric parameters and repeat the process until χ^2 is acceptable. This algorithm, and a few variants of it, has been tested by numerical experiments. It usually fails to converge if more than very few abscissae need to be corrected. Correction by trial and error leads to the correct solution sooner or later but is very time consuming.

A much more promising approach would be to adjust only the five astrometric parameters instead of the many abscissa corrections. This requires a different measure of goodness-of-fit, taking into account the periodicity of the

grid. For instance the 'circulant' chi-square,

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum_j \sigma_{ji}^{-2} \frac{\sin^2[\pi(\Delta T_{ji} - \hat{\Delta T}_{ji})/s]}{(\pi/s)^2}, \quad (13.2)$$

has the desired property of being indifferent to shifts by $\pm ns$, while $\chi_c^2 \propto \chi^2$ when all residuals are small compared to s . In contrast to χ^2 it is however multimodal as function of the astrometric parameters and finding the global minimum will require some probing of the five-dimensional parameter space. Since the parallax and proper motions are usually known to within a few tenths of an arcsec, the probing can usually be confined to the $(\Delta\alpha_0 \ \Delta\delta_0)$ plane. For an a priori uncertainty of 1.5 arcsec (rms), some 100 points may have to be probed in order to locate the global minimum. The local minimum in the vicinity of each point must be found by a couple of iterations. Having found the global minimum, the abscissa corrections are modified accordingly, viz.

$$\Delta T_{ji} := \Delta T_{ji} - s \cdot \text{entier}[(\Delta T_{ji} - \hat{\Delta T}_{ji})/s + 0.5]. \quad (13.3)$$

If, after such adjustments by $\pm ns$, the abscissa residuals are still unsatisfactory, it may be due either to duplicity (multiplicity) of the programme star or to a spurious abscissa result. The pattern of residuals should give some indication on this; e.g. if similar residuals are obtained when the star is scanned in a particular direction, duplicity is the likely cause. A single abscissa with outstanding residual may perhaps be excluded already at this stage, at least if the set solution also gives reason to doubt this particular observation; but as a rule one should not discard any observation before the possible duplicity has been examined.

14. TREATMENT OF MULTIPLE STARS

This section deals with the interconnected problems of detecting non-single stars and determining the astrometric parameters of the individual components. It is instructive to begin with a rather simplified analytical study of what happens when the periodic grid scans an object consisting of two point sources. In (6.3) let us neglect the background ($B = 0$) and overtones ($m = 1$) and introduce the modulation phase $\Psi = 2\pi G$, where G is the instantaneous grid coordinate of the brighter component. The resulting intensity due to the bright star is then

$$I_1 = I_0 [1 + M \cos \Psi], \quad (14.1)$$

where the subscript has been dropped in M_1 and $v_1 = 0$. If the second star is fainter by Δm magnitudes and displaced a distance d along the scanning direction, its contribution to the modulated intensity will be

$$I_2 = f I_0 [1 + M \cos(\Psi + \Lambda)], \quad (14.2)$$

where $f = \text{dex}(-0.4\Delta m)$ and $\Lambda = (2\pi/s)d$. s is the grid period. Combining (14.1) and (14.2) we get for the total intensity

$$I = I_1 + I_2 = (1+f)I_0 [1 + M' \cos(\Psi + \lambda)], \quad (14.3)$$

where

$$M' = M \frac{(1 + 2f \cos \Lambda + f^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + f}, \quad (14.4)$$

$$\lambda = \arctan \frac{f \sin \Lambda}{1 + f \cos \Lambda}. \quad (14.5)$$

Comparison with (14.1) shows that the fainter component influences the intensity modulation in three ways: (i) the average intensity increases by the factor $1+f$; (ii) the modulation factor is decreased by a factor (M'/M) as given by (14.4); (iii) the signal is phase shifted by the angle λ corresponding to an apparent image displacement of $(s/2\pi)\lambda$ arcsec. The first two effects will have little practical value for double-star detection, mainly because of the relatively poor photometric calibration of the IDT and the uncertain background intensity. Thus we shall concentrate on the phase shift effect and ask the following two questions: How bright must the fainter component be in order to be detectable? Which is the minimum separation of the components? It will be assumed that abscissa displacements, in order to be detected, must be at least of the same size as the typical abscissa mean errors, or about 3 mas for relatively bright stars and about 8 mas for stars of magnitude 12-13.

For a given brightness ratio (f) maximum apparent displacement is obtained with $\cos \Lambda = -f$, viz.

$$[(s/2\pi)\lambda]_{\max} = (s/2\pi) \arcsin f \approx fs/2\pi \quad (f \ll 1). \quad (14.6)$$

With $s = 1100$ mas we find $fs/2\pi > 3$ mas or 8 mas for $\Delta m < 4.4$ and 3.4 mag, respectively.

For close pairs the phase shift (14.5) must be related to the phase shift corresponding to the photocentre of the pair, i.e. the barycentre of the light

distribution of the image. The photocentric phase shift is simply

$$\lambda_{pc} = \frac{f}{1+f} \Lambda. \quad (14.7)$$

It is seen that $\lambda_{pc} \approx \lambda$ for small Λ so that the photocentre is effectively observed for close pairs. Because of the orbital motions of the components, the photocentre describes an ellipse with respect to the uniformly moving mass centre of the system. For most pairs, however, the curvature of the arc covered in a few years will be negligible and the resulting apparent motion of the photocentre is adequately represented by the same five astrometric parameters as used for single stars. The duplicity of such a pair cannot be detected by HIPPARCOS.

Detection thus depends on the difference $\lambda - \lambda_{pc}$ (rather than on λ), since this may cause model mismatch when the object is scanned in different directions. For small Λ we have

$$\lambda - \lambda_{pc} = -\frac{1}{6} \frac{f(1-f)}{(1+f)^3} \Lambda^3 + O(\Lambda^5). \quad (14.8)$$

The largest difference is thus obtained with $f = 2 - \sqrt{3}$ or $\Delta m \approx 1.4$, for which $\lambda - \lambda_{pc} \approx -0.016 \Lambda^3$. In this case $(s/2\pi)(\lambda - \lambda_{pc}) > 3$ mas or 8 mas for $d \gtrsim 0''.18$ and $0''.25$, respectively.

When the second harmonic is taken into account these criteria are somewhat sharpened. The relative shifts of the first and second harmonics is an additional, and possibly more sensitive, indicator of multiplicity. The phase shift of the second harmonic, λ_2 , is obtained by putting $\Lambda := 2\Lambda$ in (14.5); the relative displacement of the harmonics is, for small Λ ,

$$(s/2\pi)(\frac{1}{2}\lambda_2 - \lambda) \approx 3(s/2\pi)(\lambda - \lambda_{pc}). \quad (14.9)$$

It is worth noting that both $\lambda - \lambda_{pc}$ and $\frac{1}{2}\lambda_2 - \lambda$ vanish for $f = 1$, i.e. when the two components are equally bright. This is natural because the object is then symmetric (with respect to the photocentre) while phase shifts are caused by asymmetry. The effect on the modulation amplitude is on the other hand at its maximum for $f = 1$ ($\Delta m = 0$), when (14.4) reduces to $(M'/M) = \cos(\Lambda/2)$ and, for the second harmonic, $(M_2'/M_2) = \cos(\Lambda)$. E.g. for $d = 0''.18$ we have $(M'/M) \approx 0.87$ and $(M_2'/M_2) \approx 0.52$, which should easily be detected.

Based on these considerations we shall provisionally define a 'multiple star' as any group of two or more stars with the following characteristics:

- (a) if the stars are numbered 1, 2, ... in order of non-increasing brightness, $m_1 \leq m_2 \leq \dots$, we have $m_1 < 13$ and $m_2, m_3, \dots < \min(16, m_1 + 4.5)$;

(b) all components can be enclosed in a circle of radius $15''$;

(c) the minimum separation between any two components is $0''.15$.

These are the cases which are potentially troublesome in the sense that the photocentre is not automatically obtained by treating the objects as single stars; they are also the cases for which there is some chance of detecting the multiplicity from HIPPARCOS data alone.

Multiplicity, as defined above, can be detected on three different and independent grounds:

- (i) a priori: multiplicity indicated by Input Catalogue;
- (ii) from light-curve mismatch during location estimation phase (Section 10);
- (iii) from absolute abscissa mismatch during back-substitution (Section 13).

The latter two effects should be measured by means of suitable statistics. For the light-curve mismatch we may define the statistic

$$y_1 = \sum_{\kappa} \frac{1}{2} (\underline{b} - \hat{\underline{b}})' \underline{F} (\underline{b} - \hat{\underline{b}}), \quad (14.10)$$

i.e. the log likelihood ratio of the unconstrained multiple-star hypothesis H_m to the constrained single-star hypothesis H_g [cf. (10.9)], summed over all frames in which the star is observed. Under H_g each term in (14.10) is approximately chi-square distributed with two degrees of freedom; so y_1 will have a chi-square distribution with $2\nu_1$ d.o.f., $\nu_1 = \sum_{\kappa} 1$.

Similarly for the abscissa mismatch we may take

$$y_2 = \min(\chi_c^2), \quad (14.11)$$

cf. (13.2), which under H_g has a chi-square distribution with $\nu_2 - 5$ d.o.f., $\nu_2 = \sum_j 1$.

Note that y_1 may be accumulated for each star as the IDT data processing proceeds and is therefore available immediately after completion of the mission, while y_2 is obtained only after the three-step solution. Thus y_1 and the a priori information should be used in selecting the PRS stars, while final detection of multiplicity of the remaining stars must await the back-substitution and y_2 . (For PRS stars the equivalent of y_2 is obtained from PRS residuals.) Final detection of multiplicity will use a criterion of the form

$$C(y_1, y_2 \mid \nu_1, \nu_2) > C_0 \quad \vee \quad (\text{multiple in Input Catalogue}), \quad (14.12)$$

where the function C and critical level C_0 are to be determined after careful study of the theoretical and empirical distribution of (y_1, y_2) , using both

simulated and real data.

Once multiplicity of a given star has been established, it will be necessary to introduce additional astrometric and photometric model parameters to describe the relative positions, motions, and intensities of the different components. This is not a very well-defined problem since one can think of an infinite number of different models of increasing complexity, and since perfect agreement with observed data can always be obtained with a sufficiently complex model. Thus the appropriate model must be selected according to criteria to be defined. In many cases where a priori information is available the selection may be easy, but in general one would have to test a whole sequence of models (or hypotheses) of increasing complexity in order to find the least complex (or most probable, if a priori probabilities can be defined) model consistent with observations. Such a sequence of models may roughly be as follows (the number of additional model parameters is given in parentheses):

- H_1 : two components with negligible relative motion (3);
- H_2 : two components with non-negligible but linear relative motion (5);
- H_3 : (optical binary) same as H_2 but the components have different parallax (6)
- H_4 : three components with negligible relative motion (6);
- ... etc.

As an illustration of the determination of the additional parameters we discuss here only the case H_1 , which however is expected to be by far the most important one.

As additional parameters we choose the intensity ratio $f = \text{dex}(-0.4\Delta m) \leq 1$ and the the relative position of the fainter component with respect to the brighter, $da = (\alpha_{o2} - \alpha_{o1}) \cos \delta_{o1}$, $dd = \delta_{o2} - \delta_{o1}$, where $(\alpha_{oi} \ \delta_{oi})$ is the barycentric position of component i . The separation in abscissa is

$$d = v_2 - v_1 \approx da \sin \theta + dd \cos \theta, \quad (14.13)$$

where θ is the position angle of the scanning direction as defined by the reference great circle. As before we put $\Lambda = (2\pi/s)d$. The IDT signal parameters b become, instead of (10.6),

$$\left. \begin{aligned} b_1 &= [B + (1+f)I_o] \Delta t \\ b_2 &= M_1 I_o \Delta t [1 + 2f \cos \Lambda + f^2]^{1/2} \\ b_3 &= 2\pi \Delta G + \lambda(f, \Lambda) \\ b_4 &= M_2 I_o \Delta t [1 + 2f \cos(2\Lambda) + f^2]^{1/2} \cos[v_2 + 2\lambda(f, \Lambda) - \lambda(f, 2\Lambda)] \\ b_5 &= M_2 I_o \Delta t [1 + 2f \cos(2\Lambda) + f^2]^{1/2} \sin[v_2 + 2\lambda(f, \Lambda) - \lambda(f, 2\Lambda)] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14.14)$$

where the function $\lambda(f, \Lambda)$ is defined by (14.5) and I_0 and ΔG refer to the brighter component.

At this point it should be noted that ΔG may be corrected for distortions and attitude errors by means of (11.8) and also put on an absolute abscissa scale by application of the known abscissa zero point corrections. Thus corrected, ΔG (and b_3) can be treated exactly as the absolute abscissa corrections e.g. when combining results from different sets in order to get the five astrometric parameters. The ΔG used below should be interpreted in this way.

For given (f, Λ) it is seen that $\underline{b}$ is constrained in analogy with (10.7) but with M_ℓ, v_2 replaced by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_\ell^- &= M_\ell [1 + 2f \cos(\ell\Lambda) + f^2]^{1/2} / (1+f), \quad \ell = 1, 2; \\ v_2^- &= v_2 + 2\lambda(f, \Lambda) - \lambda(f, 2\Lambda). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14.15)$$

Performing the location estimation as described in Section 10 but with these modified constraints yields a new parameter vector $\underline{b}$ with covariance $\underline{F}^{-1} - \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{C}' (\underline{C} \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{C}')^{-1} \underline{C} \underline{F}^{-1}$, from which $\Delta G = [b_3 - \lambda(f, \Lambda)] / (2\pi)$ is obtained with its variance. Since this ΔG refers to a point object (the brighter component), its five astrometric parameters can be derived exactly as for single stars as described in Section 13. Goodness-of-fit statistics y_1, y_2 are also obtained from (14.10) and (14.11).

In this way a combined statistic like $C(y_1, y_2)$ can be computed as a function only of the multiplicity parameters $f, da,$ and dd , which are consequently estimated by finding the global minimum of $C(f, da, dd)$.

An alternative approach, which may also be very efficient for resolving slit ambiguities, would be based on methods for direct reconstruction of the two-dimensional image from the Fourier components sampled by the grid. Writing the single-star light curve (6.4) in the form

$$I = \sum_{\ell=-2}^{\ell=+2} A_\ell \exp(-i\ell H), \quad (14.16)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and $H = 2\pi\tilde{G}$, we have the complex coefficients

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A_{-2} &= \frac{1}{2} M_2 I_0 \Delta t \exp(-i v_2) \exp(i 4\pi \Delta G) \\ A_{-1} &= \frac{1}{2} M_1 I_0 \Delta t \exp(i 2\pi \Delta G) \\ A_0 &= (B + I_0) \Delta t \\ A_1 &= \frac{1}{2} M_1 I_0 \Delta t \exp(-i 2\pi \Delta G) \\ A_2 &= \frac{1}{2} M_2 I_0 \Delta t \exp(i v_2) \exp(-i 4\pi \Delta G) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14.17)$$

Now if da_i, dd_i are the coordinates of component i with respect to the a priori (Input Catalogue) position used for computing $\tilde{G}$, and I_i are the corresponding intensities, the multiple-star light curve can be written

$$I = \sum_{\ell=-2}^{\ell=+2} C_{\ell} \exp(-i\ell H), \quad (14.18)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_{-2} &= Z_{-2} \sum_i I_i \exp[i2(u dd_i + v da_i)], & Z_{-2} &= \frac{1}{2} M_2 \Delta t \exp(-iv_2) \\ C_{-1} &= Z_{-1} \sum_i I_i \exp[i(u dd_i + v da_i)], & Z_{-1} &= \frac{1}{2} M_1 \Delta t \\ C_0 &= Z_0 [B + \sum_i I_i], & Z_0 &= \Delta t \\ C_1 &= Z_1 \sum_i I_i \exp[-i(u dd_i + v da_i)], & Z_1 &= \frac{1}{2} M_1 \Delta t \\ C_2 &= Z_2 \sum_i I_i \exp[-i2(u dd_i + v da_i)], & Z_2 &= \frac{1}{2} M_2 \Delta t \exp(iv_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14.19)$$

and

$$u = (2\pi/s) \cos \theta, \quad v = (2\pi/s) \sin \theta. \quad (14.20)$$

Thus, if the multiple star is regarded as an image in the dd, da plane,

$$J(dd, da) = \sum_i I_i \delta(dd - dd_i) \delta(da - da_i), \quad (14.21)$$

it is seen that $\{C_{\ell}\}$ is the 2D Fourier transform of J sampled at the five points $(\ell u, \ell v)$ along a line in position angle θ , and multiplied by the complex constants $\{Z_{\ell}\}$.

The coefficients C_{ℓ} are however obtained from the signal parameters $\underline{b}$,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_{\pm 2} &= \frac{1}{2} (b_4 \pm ib_5) \exp(\mp i 2b_3) \\ C_{\pm 1} &= \frac{1}{2} b_2 \exp(\mp i b_3) \\ C_0 &= b_1 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14.22)$$

and division by Z_{ℓ} thus gives five points of the Fourier transform of the image. Combining scans in different position angles yields a number of points in the u, v plane on two circles of radius $2\pi/s$ and $4\pi/s$. Reconstructing the two-dimensional image is thus exactly analogous to the aperture synthesis problem in radio interferometry (with two fixed telescope spacings corresponding to $2\pi/s$ and $4\pi/s$, and different baseline orientations corresponding to the different scanning directions). It appears that well-known algorithms such as CLEAN (Högbom, 1974), which decompose the image into point sources, would be well suited for this purpose.

15. GLOBAL ADJUSTMENT TO THE FK5 SYSTEM

As explained in Section 12 the basic indeterminacy of the PRS solution depending on the undefined system orientation and rotation may be overcome e.g. by making a generalized solution, minimizing the norm of the solution vector. In a certain sense the PRS system is then globally adjusted to FK5, that is if the adjusted a priori coordinates are in FK5. The resulting system for the totality of programme stars may however not be optimally adjusted to FK5 by this process, but will in general depend for instance on the selection of PRS stars. This is not very satisfactory and will complicate the comparison of catalogues. The positions and proper motions should therefore be transformed into a Provisional HIPPARCOS System (PHS) which is uniquely defined in terms of FK5 and the observing programme as given by the Input Catalogue (IC). In the following we propose to define such a system.

PHS and FK5 shall have identical zero-points for the positions and proper motions in the following sense. Let $\tilde{\underline{u}}$ and $\underline{u}$ be the barycentric directions to a star at an epoch to be agreed upon (close to the mean epoch of PHS, around J1988.5), as given by FK5 and PHS respectively. Let $\underline{\epsilon}$ be a small misorientation vector which would bring $\underline{u}$ into coincidence with $\tilde{\underline{u}}$; more precisely, let

$$\tilde{\underline{u}} = \underline{u} + \underline{\epsilon} \wedge \tilde{\underline{u}} \quad (15.1)$$

(of course this does not determine $\underline{\epsilon}$ uniquely). Now consider all good stars common to PHS and FK5 ("good" = no multiplicity indicated by the IC), and determine a global misorientation $\underline{\epsilon}_g$ by least-squares combination of the $\underline{u} - \tilde{\underline{u}}$ differences, giving all stars equal weight. Then if $\underline{\epsilon}_g = \underline{0}$, the positional systems of PHS and FK5 have identical zero points. If $\underline{\epsilon}_g \neq \underline{0}$ the required corrections to PHS are $\underline{u} := \underline{u} + \underline{\epsilon}_g \wedge \tilde{\underline{u}}$. Similarly a global system rotation vector $\underline{\omega}_g$ may be obtained from comparison of PHS and FK5 proper motions, by least-squares solution of $-\underline{\omega}_g \wedge \tilde{\underline{u}} = \dot{\underline{u}} - \dot{\tilde{\underline{u}}}$. The proper motions of the two systems have identical zero points if $\underline{\omega}_g = \underline{0}$.

In terms of celestial coordinates at the mean epoch, $(\alpha_o \delta_o \mu_\alpha \mu_\delta)$ in PHS and $(\tilde{\alpha}_o \tilde{\delta}_o \tilde{\mu}_\alpha \tilde{\mu}_\delta)$ in FK5, the observation equations for $\underline{\epsilon}_g$ and $\underline{\omega}_g$ become

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sin \tilde{\delta}_o \cos \tilde{\alpha}_o & \sin \tilde{\delta}_o \sin \tilde{\alpha}_o & -\cos \tilde{\delta}_o \\ -\sin \tilde{\alpha}_o & \cos \tilde{\alpha}_o & 0 \end{pmatrix} \underline{\epsilon}_g = \begin{pmatrix} (\alpha_o - \tilde{\alpha}_o) \cos \tilde{\delta}_o \\ \delta_o - \tilde{\delta}_o \end{pmatrix} \quad (15.2)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{(ditto)} \end{pmatrix} \underline{\omega}_g = \begin{pmatrix} (\mu_\alpha - \tilde{\mu}_\alpha) \cos \tilde{\delta}_o \\ \mu_\delta - \tilde{\mu}_\delta \end{pmatrix} \quad (15.3)$$

Appendix A

NOTATIONAL CONVENTIONS

Vectors and matrices are denoted by underbarred Roman or Greek letters, e.g. $\underline{a}$, $\underline{A}$. As far as practicable, lower-case letters are used for vectors (column matrices) and capital letters for matrices with more than one column. $\underline{I}_n$ or $\underline{I}$ is the identity matrix of dimension (n,n). A prime (') marks the transposed matrix (vector); hence $\underline{a}'\underline{b}$ is the scalar product of vectors $\underline{a}$ and $\underline{b}$. The Euclidean norm of a vector $\underline{a}$ is $|\underline{a}| = (\underline{a}'\underline{a})^{1/2}$. The time derivative of a vector $\underline{a} = (a_1 \ a_2 \ \dots \ a_n)'$ is $\dot{\underline{a}} = (d/dt)\underline{a} = (da_1/dt \ da_2/dt \ \dots \ da_n/dt)'$. Time derivatives of matrices, e.g. $\dot{\underline{A}} = (d/dt)\underline{A}$, are similarly defined by the derivatives of its elements.

Special among the square matrices are orthogonal transformations (or bases) which may be distinguished by an underlining tilde ($\underline{\sim}$). $\underline{\sim}A$ is an n-base if and only if $\underline{\sim}A'\underline{\sim}A = \underline{\sim}A\underline{\sim}A' = \underline{I}_n$ ($\underline{I}_n$ is of course a base too) and consists of n orthogonal unit n-vectors. The coordinates of the arbitrary n-vector $\underline{r}$ in base $\underline{\sim}A$ are given by the elements of $\underline{\sim}A'\underline{r}$. In base $\underline{\sim}B$ the coordinates of the same vector are given by $\underline{\sim}B'\underline{r} = \underline{\sim}B'(\underline{\sim}A\underline{\sim}A')\underline{r} = (\underline{\sim}B'\underline{\sim}A)(\underline{\sim}A'\underline{r})$; hence $\underline{\sim}B'\underline{\sim}A$ is the transformation from base $\underline{\sim}A$ to base $\underline{\sim}B$. A 3-base is right-handed if its determinant equals +1.

For a 3-vector $\underline{r} = (r_1 \ r_2 \ r_3)'$ we define the (3,3)-matrix

$$\underline{r}_\wedge = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -r_3 & r_2 \\ r_3 & 0 & -r_1 \\ -r_2 & r_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

If $\underline{\epsilon}$ is an infinitesimal 3-vector, then $\underline{I} + \underline{\epsilon}_\wedge$ is the orthogonal transformation corresponding to a rotation about $\underline{\epsilon}$ by the angle $|\underline{\epsilon}|$.

If $\underline{a}$, $\underline{b}$, $\underline{c}$, $\underline{d}$ are 3-vectors and $\underline{\sim}A$ a right-handed 3-base, we have

$$(\underline{a}_\wedge)' = -\underline{a}_\wedge \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\underline{a}_\wedge \underline{b} = -\underline{b}_\wedge \underline{a} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\underline{a}'\underline{b}_\wedge \underline{c} = \underline{b}'\underline{c}_\wedge \underline{a} = \underline{c}'\underline{a}_\wedge \underline{b} = \det(\underline{a} \ \underline{b} \ \underline{c}) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\underline{a}_\wedge \underline{b}_\wedge \underline{c} = (\underline{a}'\underline{c})\underline{b} - (\underline{a}'\underline{b})\underline{c} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$(\underline{a}_\wedge \underline{b})'(\underline{c}_\wedge \underline{d}) = (\underline{a}'\underline{c})(\underline{b}'\underline{d}) - (\underline{a}'\underline{d})(\underline{b}'\underline{c}) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$(\underline{\sim}A'\underline{a})_\wedge = \underline{\sim}A'\underline{a}_\wedge \underline{\sim}A \quad (\text{A.7})$$

SQUARE ROOT INFORMATION SMOOTHING

Following Bierman (1977) we shall briefly outline an algorithm for square root information smoothing of a discrete linear system. Variants of this algorithm can be applied to the a posteriori attitude reconstitution being a part of the scientific data processing for Hipparcos.

We are concerned with least-squares estimation of an n-dimensional parameter vector $\underline{s}$ (state vector) describing the time-varying state of a dynamical system. The evolution of the system is represented by a stochastic difference equation

$$\underline{s}_{j+1} = \underline{\Phi}_j \underline{s}_j + \underline{G}_j \underline{w}_j, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, N, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

in which $\underline{s}_j$ is the state vector at time t_j , $\underline{\Phi}_j$ is a non-singular transition matrix (n,n), $\underline{w}_j$ is a p-dimensional vector of process noise, and $\underline{G}_j$ an (n,p)-matrix. The process noise is characterized by the mean $E(\underline{w}_j)$ and covariance $\text{Cov}(\underline{w}_j)$. Without loss of generality (by redefining $\underline{G}_j$ if necessary) we may assume the latter to be the identity matrix of dimension (p,p):

$$E(\underline{w}_j) = \bar{\underline{w}}_j, \quad \text{Cov}(\underline{w}_j) = \underline{I}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, N. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The a priori knowledge of the system is represented by the known matrices $\underline{\Phi}_j$, $\underline{G}_j$, $\bar{\underline{w}}_j$, $\underline{I}$, and possibly some information on the initial state vector $\underline{s}_0$. The latter is formally expressed as a normalized system of a priori observation equations

$$\tilde{\underline{R}}_0 \underline{s}_0 + \tilde{\underline{v}}_0 = \tilde{\underline{z}}_0 \quad (\text{B.3})$$

(the tilde $\tilde{}$ denoting a priori quantities), where $\tilde{\underline{R}}_0$ is an upper-triangular (n,n)-matrix and the error vector $\tilde{\underline{v}}_0$ has zero mean and unit covariance. $\tilde{\underline{R}}_0$ is thus the square root (Cholesky factor) of the information matrix $\tilde{\underline{R}}_0' \tilde{\underline{R}}_0$ obtained by forming the normal equations from (A.3); if this is non-singular the a priori least-squares estimate of $\underline{s}_0$ is $\tilde{\underline{s}}_0 = (\tilde{\underline{R}}_0' \tilde{\underline{R}}_0)^{-1} \tilde{\underline{R}}_0' \tilde{\underline{z}}_0$, with covariance $(\tilde{\underline{R}}_0' \tilde{\underline{R}}_0)^{-1}$. Note however that (B.3) is applicable also when there is no a priori information on $\underline{s}_0$ ($\tilde{\underline{R}}_0 = \underline{0}$) or when the information matrix is singular.

The term "square root information smoothing" derives from using triangular observation equations similar to (B.3) as a statistical description of various vectors, rather than using e.g. the corresponding normal equations or the expected vector and covariance matrix. Most importantly, the algorithm permits direct updating of the "square roots", without going via the information matrix, as in traditional least-squares estimation.

Apart from the a priori system knowledge contained in (B.1)-(B.3), the system may be observed at various times. After linearization and normalization each scalar measurement results in a linear observation equation with unit uncertainty. If $m_j \geq 0$ scalar measurements are performed at time t_j , the observation equations become

$$\underline{A}_j \underline{s}_j + \underline{v}_j = \underline{z}_j, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, N, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where $\underline{A}_j$ is an (m_j, n) matrix and $\underline{v}_j$, $\underline{z}_j$ are m_j -vectors containing the measurement errors (zero mean, unit covariance) and measurements, respectively.

Since (B.1)-(B.4) express all information available up to and including time t_N it follows that the smoothed (least-squares) estimates $\underline{s}_j^*$, $j = 0, 1, \dots, N$, should minimize the functional

$$J_N = \left| \tilde{\underline{R}}_0 \underline{s}_0 - \tilde{\underline{z}}_0 \right|^2 + \sum_{j=0}^N \left(\left| \underline{A}_j \underline{s}_j - \underline{z}_j \right|^2 + \left| \underline{w}_j - \bar{\underline{w}}_j \right|^2 \right) \quad (\text{B.5})$$

subject to the constraints (B.1).

It is of course perfectly possible to solve for $\underline{s}_j^*$ by conventional least-squares batch processing of the observation equations implicit in (B.5). However, the recursions described below take full advantage of the structure of these equations in order to facilitate computations and reduce storage requirements to a minimum. In addition, the square root information processing is known to be numerically more accurate than forming and solving normal equations (essentially because the condition number of the Cholesky factors is the square root of that of the corresponding normal equations, which are therefore usually more ill-conditioned).

To obtain the desired recursions consider first the case $N = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} J_0 &= \left| \tilde{\underline{R}}_0 \underline{s}_0 - \tilde{\underline{z}}_0 \right|^2 + \left| \underline{A}_0 \underline{s}_0 - \underline{z}_0 \right|^2 + \left| \underline{w}_0 - \bar{\underline{w}}_0 \right|^2 \\ &= \left| \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\underline{R}}_0 \\ \underline{A}_0 \end{pmatrix} \underline{s}_0 - \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\underline{z}}_0 \\ \underline{z}_0 \end{pmatrix} \right|^2 + \left| \underline{w}_0 - \bar{\underline{w}}_0 \right|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

It is possible to find an orthogonal transformation $\underline{Q}$ which triangularizes the augmented matrix containing $\tilde{\underline{R}}_0$ and $\underline{A}_0$, viz.

$$Q \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{R}_0 \\ \underline{A}_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{R}_0 \\ \underline{0} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where $\hat{R}_0$ is an upper-triangular (n,n)-matrix. Since orthogonal transformations preserve the norm of any vector we find

$$\begin{aligned} J_0 &= \left| \begin{pmatrix} \hat{R}_0 \\ \underline{0} \end{pmatrix} \underline{s}_0 - \begin{pmatrix} \hat{z}_0 \\ \underline{e}_0 \end{pmatrix} \right|^2 + \left| \underline{w}_0 - \underline{\bar{w}}_0 \right|^2 \\ &= \left| \underline{e}_0 \right|^2 + \left| \hat{R}_0 \underline{s}_0 - \hat{z}_0 \right|^2 + \left| \underline{w}_0 - \underline{\bar{w}}_0 \right|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

where $(\hat{z}_0' \ \underline{e}_0')' = Q(\tilde{z}_0' \ \underline{z}_0')'$. In practice the triangularization is carried out by means of a succession of n elementary Householder transformations of the augmented matrix (for j = 0)

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{R}_j & \tilde{z}_j \\ \underline{A}_j & \underline{z}_j \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{Q} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{R}_j & \hat{z}_j \\ \underline{0} & \underline{e}_j \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.9})$$

A Fortran algorithm for such partial triangularization of matrices is given in Appendix C.

Clearly J_0 is minimized by $\hat{\underline{s}}_0 = \hat{R}_0^{-1} \hat{\underline{z}}_0$, which is the filtered estimate of $\underline{s}_0$ (i.e. the estimate based on all data up to and including t_j , j = 0). Eliminating $\underline{s}_0$ by means of (B.1) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} J_0 &= \left| \underline{e}_0 \right|^2 + \left| \begin{pmatrix} \underline{I} & \underline{0} \\ -\hat{R}_0 \hat{\phi}_0^{-1} \underline{G}_0 & \hat{R}_0 \hat{\phi}_0^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{w}_0 \\ \underline{s}_1 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \underline{\bar{w}}_0 \\ \hat{\underline{z}}_0 \end{pmatrix} \right|^2 \\ &= \left| \underline{e}_0 \right|^2 + \left| \begin{pmatrix} \underline{U}_0 & \underline{V}_0 \\ \underline{0} & \tilde{R}_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{w}_0 \\ \underline{s}_1 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\underline{w}}_0 \\ \tilde{\underline{z}}_1 \end{pmatrix} \right|^2 \\ &= \left| \underline{e}_0 \right|^2 + \left| \tilde{R}_1 \underline{s}_1 - \tilde{\underline{z}}_1 \right|^2 + \left| \underline{U}_0 \underline{w}_0 + \underline{V}_0 \underline{s}_1 - \tilde{\underline{w}}_0 \right|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

where $\underline{U}_0$, $\underline{V}_0$, $\tilde{\underline{w}}_0$, $\tilde{R}_1$, and $\tilde{\underline{z}}_1$ are obtained by the orthogonal transformation (for j = 0)

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{I} & \underline{0} & \underline{\bar{w}}_j \\ -\hat{\underline{R}}_j \underline{\Phi}_j^{-1} \underline{G}_j & \hat{\underline{R}}_j \underline{\Phi}_j^{-1} & \hat{\underline{z}}_j \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{\underline{Q}} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{U}_j & \underline{V}_j & \underline{\tilde{w}}_j \\ \underline{0} & \underline{\tilde{R}}_{j+1} & \underline{\tilde{z}}_{j+1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

in which $\underline{U}_j$ is upper-triangular ($\underline{Q}$ is of course not the same transformation as in (A.9).)

The term $|\underline{\tilde{R}}_1 \underline{s}_1 - \underline{\tilde{z}}_1|^2$ in (B.10) corresponds to the a priori information on $\underline{s}_1$, i.e. the estimate based on data prior to t_1 . This information may be combined with the new data at t_1 , $\underline{A}_1 \underline{s}_1 + \underline{v}_1 = \underline{z}_1$, by means of the transformation (B.9) for $j = 1$, whereupon the transition matrix $\underline{\Phi}_1$ and process noise information $\underline{\bar{w}}_1$ may be incorporated by means of (B.11), and so forth. It is seen that such recursive processing for $j = 0, 1, \dots, N$ enables the least-squares functional J_N to be written in the form

$$J_N = \sum_{j=0}^N |\underline{e}_j|^2 + \sum_{j=0}^N |\underline{U}_j \underline{w}_j + \underline{V}_j \underline{s}_{j+1} - \underline{\tilde{w}}_j|^2 + |\underline{\tilde{R}}_{N+1} \underline{s}_{N+1} - \underline{\tilde{z}}_{N+1}|^2. \quad (\text{B.12})$$

This is obviously minimized if $\underline{s}_j$ and $\underline{w}_j$ are chosen such that all terms except the first sum vanish; the remainder is the sum of the squared residuals. With (B.1) this gives the following backward recursion for the smoothed estimates:

$$\underline{s}_{N+1}^* = \underline{\tilde{R}}_{N+1}^{-1} \underline{\tilde{z}}_{N+1} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \underline{w}_j^* &= \underline{U}_j^{-1} (\underline{\tilde{w}}_j - \underline{V}_j \underline{s}_{j+1}^*) \\ \underline{s}_j^* &= \underline{\Phi}_j^{-1} (\underline{s}_{j+1}^* - \underline{G}_j \underline{w}_j^*) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad j = N, N-1, \dots, 0 \quad (\text{B.14})$$

During the forward recursions it is necessary to store only $\underline{U}_j$, $\underline{V}_j$, and $\underline{\tilde{w}}_j$, and accumulate the sum of $|\underline{e}_j|^2$ (if J_N is required), while $\underline{\tilde{R}}_j$, $\underline{\tilde{z}}_j$, $\hat{\underline{R}}_j$, and $\hat{\underline{z}}_j$ may be sequentially overwritten. Note that the triangular form of $\underline{\tilde{R}}_j$ and $\underline{U}_j$ makes the solution of $\underline{s}_{N+1}^*$ and $\underline{w}_j^*$ an explicit process. If the dynamical system is stationary (as in the attitude determination problem) the transition matrix $\underline{\Phi}_j$ (and $\underline{G}_j$) is independent of j , which greatly reduces storage and requires the transition matrix to be inverted only once.

The covariance of the smoothed state vector, $\underline{P}_j^*$, can be obtained by backward recursions, starting from

$$\underline{P}_{N+1}^* = \underline{R}_{N+1}^{-1} \underline{R}_{N+1}'^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.15})$$

Eliminating $\underline{w}_j^*$ in (B.14) we have

$$\underline{s}_j^* = \underline{\phi}_j^{-1} [(\underline{I} + \underline{L}_j \underline{V}_j) \underline{s}_{j+1}^* - \underline{L}_j \underline{\tilde{w}}_j], \quad j = N, N-1, \dots, 0 \quad (\text{B.16})$$

where

$$\underline{L}_j = \underline{G}_j \underline{U}_j^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.17})$$

Since $\text{Cov}(\underline{\tilde{w}}_j) = \text{Cov}(\underline{Q} \underline{w}_j) = \text{Cov}(\underline{w}_j) = \underline{I}$ we obtain the recursion

$$\underline{P}_j^* = \underline{\phi}_j^{-1} [(\underline{I} + \underline{L}_j \underline{V}_j) \underline{P}_{j+1}^* (\underline{I} + \underline{L}_j \underline{V}_j)' + \underline{L}_j \underline{L}_j'] \underline{\phi}_j^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.18})$$

It is obvious that the amount of computations is considerably reduced if only the smoothed estimate, $\underline{s}_j^*$, is required, and not the smoothed covariance, $\underline{P}_j^*$. Counts of arithmetic operations for the two cases are given by Bierman (1974).

Appendix C

A FORTRAN SUBROUTINE FOR PARTIAL TRIANGULARIZATION OF A MATRIX S(NR,NC)
BY ORTHOGONAL TRANSFORMATION

(from Bierman, 1977, pp. 155 - 157)

Input:

NR, NC = number of rows and columns of S; $NR \leq 50$ (dimension of V)
M = the M first columns of S are triangularized; $1 \leq M \leq \min(NR, NC)$
S = the matrix to be triangularized

Output:

S = the triangularized matrix; $S(I,J) = 0$ for $I > J$ and $J \leq M$

```

SUBROUTINE TRIANG (NR, NC, M, S)
DIMENSION V(50), S(1,1)          (V is a work vector of dimension  $\geq NR$ )
ZERO = 0.
ONE = 1.
DO 5 J = 1, M
  SIGMA = ZERO
  DO 1 I = J, NR
    V(I) = S(I,J)
    S(I,J) = ZERO
1    SIGMA = SIGMA + V(I)**2
  IF (SIGMA .LE. ZERO) GO TO 5
  SIGMA = SQRT(SIGMA)
  IF (V(J) .GT. ZERO) SIGMA = -SIGMA
  S(J,J) = SIGMA
  V(J) = V(J) - SIGMA
  SIGMA = ONE/(SIGMA*V(J))
  IF (J .GE. NC) GO TO 5
  DO 4 K = J+1, NC
    ALFA = ZERO
    DO 2 I = J, NR
2      ALFA = ALFA + S(I,K)*V(I)
    ALFA = ALFA*SIGMA
    DO 3 I = J, NR
3      S(I,K) = S(I,K) + ALFA*V(I)
4    CONTINUE
5  CONTINUE
RETURN
END

```

Appendix D

SOLUTION OF RANK DEFICIENT NORMAL EQUATIONS

Both in the set solutions and the PRS solution we are facing the computational difficulty that the normal equations based purely on HIPPARCOS data are (or should be!) singular: the rank deficiency should be one for a set solution (due to the undefined abscissa zero point) and six for the PRS solution (three orientation angles and three components of the system rotation). The problem can only be overcome by introducing external information, either in the form of postulated properties of the desired solution, or in the form of a priori (but inexact) data. In principle the inclusion of postulated properties means a constrained solution, while a priori data can always be expressed as uncorrelated observation equations of unit weight.

The actual choice of method may be guided entirely by numerical and computational considerations since, from a scientific point of view, there is no reason to prefer one solution to another as long as both are equally consistent with observational data. This is explicitly so for the set solutions for which the zero points will anyway be determined at a later stage. It is not quite so obvious for the PRS solution, for which a provisional adaptation to FK5 (say) may be very desirable. However, the resulting system of positions and proper motions for all HIPPARCOS stars, not only PRS, must in the end be analysed with respect to FK5 and probably adjusted to it by means of small changes in orientation and rotation. Thus there is no reason to adhere very strictly to FK5 in the PRS solution.

Of the many possibilities to secure a unique solution we can mention:

- (i) Postulating the values of k unknowns (k = rank deficiency). This method was used in numerical simulations of the spherical reconstitution performed in Copenhagen (Hoyer et al., 1981 = Annex B). It may be quite adequate, especially for the set solutions, although the unknown(s) to be postulated should be carefully selected.
- (ii) Introducing k linear constraints and k Lagrangian multipliers. The constraints would postulate e.g. that the sum of abscissa corrections in a set is zero, or that the PRS solution agrees in a least-squares sense with FK5. This method may be numerically inaccurate and will not give a positive definite matrix, which is a complication with the Cholesky algorithm.
- (iii) Introducing a priori values of some (or all) of the unknowns as additional observations with very low weight. A serious disadvantage of

this otherwise attractive method is that the condition number of the normal equations increases, compared to that of an optimally constrained solution, by at least a factor equal to the weight ratio between the solution and the a priori data. Thus, since the weight of the PRS solution will be at least 1000 times that of FK5, one would unnecessarily lose three more digits due to rounding errors.

- (iv) Making a generalized (pseudo-) solution. The Moore-Penrose solution, for instance, is in principle constrained to the solution with minimum Euclidean norm.

More theoretical work and practical experiments are needed to decide which of these methods, if any, is suitable for the present purposes. As an example of the last method we give here an algorithm for the generalized solution which appears well suited in connexion with adjustment programmes developed at the Danish Geodetic Institute.

Let the system of normal equations be of order n and rank $r < n$. We assert, without proof, that a permutation of unknowns (rows and columns) can be found such that the upper-left (r,r) -submatrix $\underline{A}$ is positive definite. Thus the normals are written in block form

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{A} & \underline{a} \\ \underline{a}' & \underline{\alpha} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{x} \\ \underline{y} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{f} \\ \underline{g} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{D.1})$$

where $\underline{a}$ is of dimension (r,k) , $k = n - r$; and $\underline{\alpha}$ is (k,k) . $\underline{A}$ and $\underline{\alpha}$ are symmetric. Since $\underline{A}^{-1}$ exists, the rows of $\underline{A}$ are linearly independent and the same is true for the rows of $\begin{pmatrix} \underline{A} & \underline{a} \end{pmatrix}$, i.e. the first r rows of the normal equations matrix. It follows that the last k rows, $\begin{pmatrix} \underline{a}' & \underline{\alpha} \end{pmatrix}$, can be written as linear combinations of the former. If a solution to (D.1) exists, the elements of $\underline{g}$ must be the same linear combinations of the elements of $\underline{f}$. Thus we need only consider the subsystem

$$\underline{Ax} + \underline{ay} = \underline{f}, \quad (\text{D.2})$$

the remaining equations being linear combinations of these.

Equation (D.2) can be solved for $\underline{x}$ in terms of $\underline{y}$,

$$\underline{x} = \underline{A}^{-1}(\underline{f} - \underline{ay}) = \underline{p} - \underline{qy}, \quad (\text{D.3})$$

where $\underline{p} = \underline{A}^{-1}\underline{f}$ and $\underline{q} = \underline{A}^{-1}\underline{a}$. It is seen that $\begin{pmatrix} \underline{p} - \underline{qy} \\ \underline{y} \end{pmatrix}$ is a solution of (D.1) for any k -vector $\underline{y}$.

Among the infinitude of solution vectors we select the one with minimum norm, i.e. the pseudo-solution. Thus $\underline{y}$ is chosen to minimize

$$s = \begin{vmatrix} \underline{x} \\ \underline{y} \end{vmatrix}^2 = \underline{x}'\underline{x} + \underline{y}'\underline{y} = \underline{p}'\underline{p} - 2\underline{y}'\underline{q}'\underline{p} + \underline{y}'\underline{q}'\underline{q}\underline{y} + \underline{y}'\underline{y}. \quad (D.4)$$

Since

$$\frac{\partial s}{\partial \underline{y}} = -2\underline{q}'\underline{p} + 2\underline{q}'\underline{q}\underline{y} + 2\underline{y} \quad (D.5)$$

the minimizing $\underline{y}$ is obtained by solving the following system of order $k = n - r$,

$$(\underline{I}_k + \underline{q}'\underline{q})\underline{y} = \underline{q}'\underline{p}. \quad (D.6)$$

The process is readily extended to any number (m) of right-hand sides. The resulting algorithm is schematically shown in the figure below.

LITERATURE

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